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List of Abbreviations and Acronyms

EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
GA	Grant Agreement
REA	European Research Executive Agency
WP	Work Package

Executive Summary

The deliverable presents the results of the fieldwork conducted within the FIERCE project for the Work Package 2 – Feminist Movements and Democracy, in the months between M7 and M26.

The WP2 aims at understanding the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels for the development of feminist movements in eight different country contexts over the period 2010-23. This phase of mobilization, which has gained momentum since the 2010s, has been marked by the rise of transnational feminist movements, such as *Ni Una Menos* and *#MeToo*, and the simultaneous escalation of radical right and neoconservative attacks on gender rights. By examining feminist movements in Italy, Denmark, France, Turkey, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain, FIERCE aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the ways feminist activism is reshaping political landscapes, fostering democratic innovation, and resisting growing authoritarianism. It seeks to identify how gender frames and narratives are disseminated and communicated by feminist movements. The WP2 also aims at understanding conflicts and tensions within the movement. Lastly, the research wants to explore the relationship between feminist movements and other political actors.

The project has investigated feminist movements through three different research streams defined on the basis of the three different methods adopted in data-collection: Interviews, Critical Frame Analysis and Discourse Network Analysis. Through these three strands of research, we have aimed to capture feminist discourses and practices during the period between 2010-2023. The analysis has been conducted upon 240 interviews, 250 documents and 56.840 articles from newspapers. Given the nature of feminist movements, and the research attention to the movement's policy impact, the analysis has considered both grassroots activism and institutional and policy-oriented initiatives and actors.

In what follows, the executive summary provides an overview of the research results, and a short summary of each research stream. Section 3, 4, 5 presents the results of the three research streams, each introduced by an explanation of the methodological approach and an overview of the results. Finally, there is a section collecting the reports for each country case.

1. Introduction to the FIERCE Project

1.1. The FIERCE Project – Summary

FIERCE aims to provide sound theoretical and practical knowledge and tools to revitalize alliances between the feminist movement, civil society and political decision makers in a context of growing social inequalities, political disaffection and strengthening of populist radical right anti-gender actors and discourses. The research uses an interdisciplinary, multi-dimensional and multi-level framework, that aims to overcome the limitations of both disciplinary scholarships and nationalist methodologies. FIERCE develops in-depth understanding of feminist and anti-feminist/anti-gender movements, activities and discourses, and their impact on the institutional arena and on policy outcomes, focusing on the period 2010-2021. These actors, and especially the feminist movement, will be studied through frame analysis, political ethnography and Social Network Analysis on the background of key gender debates and controversies prefigured to be situated in the areas of: labour market; health and reproductive rights; LGBTQ+ rights; migration; and gender-based violence. FIERCE will cover eight case studies (France, Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey, Denmark, Poland, Spain) representing a wide variety of country contexts in socio-political, geographical and welfare terms. FIERCE moves beyond a country-based approach and provides a cross-cutting comparative analysis of the way debates and controversies on gender have influenced the dynamics and output of the policy process. Building on co-creation methods and on a strong alliance with civil society organisations, FIERCE proposes pilot actions that can reinvigorate democratic practices, in line with feminist inclusive visions for the future of democracy. FIERCE thereby sets out a bottom-up, problem-driven and impact-oriented approach, bridging academic knowledge, policy-making and bottom-up democratic strategies.

1.2. Description of WP2 and interconnections

The WP2 aims at understanding the structural and contextual conditions at national and transnational levels for the development of feminist movements in eight different country contexts over the period 2010-23. This phase of mobilization, which has gained momentum since the 2010s, has been marked by the rise of transnational feminist movements, such as *Ni Una Menos* and *#MeToo*, and the simultaneous escalation of radical right and neoconservative attacks on gender rights. By examining feminist movements in Italy, Denmark, France, Turkey, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain, FIERCE aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the ways feminist activism is reshaping political landscapes, fostering democratic innovation, and resisting growing authoritarianism. It seeks to identify how gender frames and narratives are disseminated and communicated by feminist movements. The WP2 also aims at understanding conflicts and tensions within the movement. Lastly, the research wants to explore the relationship between feminist movements and other political actors.

The work on the WP2 has been paralleled by the work on the WP1, serving as a lens to understand how both anti-gender actors and feminist movements intervene to re-shape democratic processes. Moreover, the work on the WP4 has been constantly linked to the sampling process of the fieldwork and to the definition of meaningful results, according to co-creation and participatory work done with feminist activists. Finally, the WP2, together with the WP1, will serve as the foundation to the WP3, where cross-comparative analysis will be conducted, by comprehensively linking the three research streams.

2. Summary of the results of the fieldwork

The project has investigated feminist movements through three different research streams defined on the basis of the three different methods adopted in data-collection: Interviews, Critical Frame Analysis

and Discourse Network Analysis. Through these three strands of research, we have aimed to capture feminist discourses and practices during the period between 2010-2023. The analysis has been conducted upon 240 interviews, 250 documents and 56840 articles from newspapers. Given the nature of feminist movements, and the research attention to the movement's policy impact, the analysis has considered both grassroots activism and institutional and policy-oriented initiatives and actors.

To what follows a clear and concise overview of the three research streams, outlining the methodological lines employed in each and highlighting some of the key findings is presented. The full country reports are included in the present document as external links to facilitate the reading process.

2.1. Interviews

A key component of the FIERCE project has been the collection and analysis of interviews with feminist activists and politicians, who have provided valuable insights into the strategies, discourses, and organizational models that define contemporary feminist movements. Semi-structured interviews have offered an in-depth perspective on the internal dynamics of feminist organizing, the external pressures posed by anti-gender movements, and the critical importance of intersectionality, care work, and digital activism in shaping feminist practices today.

Through 240 semi-structured interviews with diverse activists and politicians, the study captures perspectives on key issues, such as gender-based violence, reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, and labor struggles, as well as their broader fight against patriarchy and neoliberalism. Interviews covered various themes, including the history and ideology of groups, issues at the core of their activism, challenges from anti-gender movements, action repertoires, organizational structures, and alliances. This method allowed participants to articulate their experiences and the unique challenges shaped by local contexts.

Ethical standards were strictly maintained, ensuring participant confidentiality, granting anonymity and support on sensitive issues. The study's findings reveal both common struggles and country-specific challenges within the broader political and social landscapes, offering insights into how feminist movements counteract backlash while fostering solidarity and democratic innovations across Europe.

2.1.1. Key Findings

The data collected through semi-structured interviews have provided significant insights into the characteristics of contemporary feminist movements. The analysis of the new phase of feminist mobilization which started in 2010 shows that its emergence can be attributed to the confluence of different factors: first, the specific political opportunity structures, particularly in view of the challenges posed by far-right actors; the role of transnational diffusion, especially thanks to the massive mobilizations of the Ni Una Menos movement in Argentina and of the #MeToo movement in the US; furthermore, while the present cycle of feminist protest presents unique and innovative characteristics, continuities with preceding cycles of mobilization emerge as crucial in all the countries.

Regarding the main issues at the core of these mobilizations, the analysis shows that contemporary feminist movements in all the countries share a central concern for gender-based violence, which has represented the main element on which recent mobilizations have emerged. Significantly, in most of the countries the fight against gender-based violence has been articulated through a definition of violence as a structural problem, thus countering emergency-driven narratives of femicides. In some countries, the struggle against gender-based violence is framed as being against patriarchy, capitalism and racism, showing the intersectional approach adopted by the movement. The intersectional

framework has indeed become a critical paradigm in feminist activism, notably in Spain, France, Turkey, Italy, and Slovenia, addressing the overlapping and intersecting nature of various forms of oppression.

Another recurring central issue addressed by feminist movements concerns the right to abortion, which continues to be threatened in many countries. In fact, as the analysis conducted in Italy, Slovenia and Turkey shows, even when abortion is legally protected, informal obstacles to abortion, such as conscience objection and medical violence and formal neglect regarding the provision of this procedure in public hospitals, have increased over the past decade.

Contemporary feminist mobilizations also put at the core of their struggles LGBTQ+ rights. During the period under scrutiny, these have come to constitute a key field of intervention for feminist movements in Europe. In almost all the cases we have analyzed the alliance between feminist and lgbtq collectives represents a key aspect in the recent wave of mobilization.

Another key aspect of contemporary feminist movements in Europe is constituted by a renewed attention to economic inequalities, labor and care work. This is partly also the result of the increased relevance of an anti-capitalist approach within feminism, as it was highlighted especially in the cases of Italy, Spain, France, and Poland.

A central aspect for most cases is the necessity to respond to the conservative backlash and to anti-gender movements and policies. In the cases of Slovenia, Turkey, France, and Poland, this was particularly pertinent. This has also brought into question the largely reactive character of feminist movements politics in certain instances, such as the Polish one.

The national cases show significant differences in terms of the movement's organizational structures. In some cases the movement has a largely informal and non-hierarchical structure. This is the case for Italy, Spain and Greece. In other countries, movements tend to be more institutionalized such as in Denmark. In general, in most cases the movement presents a multifaceted nature in terms of organizational forms, with more grassroots groups coexisting with associations and professional organizations and institutional actors, typically political parties.

As for the repertoires of action adopted by the movements, the main forms of intervention are protest, demonstrations and more broadly the occupation of the public space with visible actions. The innovative use of performances, as part of a new repertoire was highlighted in many of the cases investigated. The analysis underlines the relevance of the digital space as an important field of intervention. Other key repertoires are direct social action and knowledge production.

When asked about their movements' outcomes, most interviewees pointed at the discursive shifts and cultural change they obtained, especially in the field of GBV. A broader awareness of the issue is recognized as having increased among the public opinion, largely thanks to the movements' initiatives.

The analysis shows significant differences in the relationship that feminist movements have with institutional actors. For instance, in Denmark there is a clear feminist affiliation among institutional actors, demonstrating support for feminist initiatives. Conversely, in other countries, this association is more nuanced or completely absent, indicating a diversity of institutional responses to feminist activism.

With regard to policy impact, in most countries feminist activists expressed frustration regarding the difficulties faced in impacting policy-making. This was especially the case in countries where the political

system appears as extremely 'closed', such as in Turkey. In other cases, despite the complex mechanism for activists to exert an influence at the policy level, significant legal and policy changes were highlighted (e.g. Spain, Slovenia, Greece, Denmark). On the side of politicians and policy-makers, the rise of the massive phase of feminist mobilizations was acknowledged and seen as empowering the actions within parties and institutions.

2.2. Critical Frame Analysis

The analysis of documents by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors (WP1) and by the feminist movements (WP2) was conducted using critical frame analysis (CFA), a second key data strain component of the FIERCE project. The analysis' stated objective was to determine how gender and gender categories are framed, utilized, disseminated, and communicated. This encompassed the scrutiny of intersectional patterns and emotions, as well as major and minor frames within the five thematic areas addressed by the project (labour market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, gender-based violence). The CFA also paid close attention to the potential policy impact or influence, as these were taken into account in the analyzed documents. The fundamental unit of analysis was campaigns, which are characterized by a long-term political process that encompasses both a policy dimension (e.g., a legislative proposal) and an activist dimension (e.g., mobilization in support of or opposition to policy change). The documents sourced within each context was then analyzed using CFA. From each national case one campaign was selected focusing on the thematic area of gender-based violence (GBV) for WP2; this after reviewing all available campaigns. Each team then determined the second campaign to be coded, according to its specific relevance within the country.

2.2.1. Key Findings

Across multiple countries, feminist campaigns on gender-based violence (GBV) reveal both shared and divergent approaches, with the "Structural Violence" frame standing out as the most significant across all cases. This frame interprets GBV as deeply rooted in societal structures, emphasizing the necessity of addressing unequal power dynamics that perpetuate violence against women. Other frames, including "Intersectionality," "Class Consciousness," "Political-Economic," and "Health and Reproductive Rights," are also present but less dominant, highlighting the complex, multidimensional nature of GBV across feminist discourses.

Social movement documents display greater diversity in frames than parliamentary debate materials, particularly in their emphasis on intersectionality. For example, topics like "Racism and Nationalism" and "LGBTQ+ Rights" are prominent only in social movement contexts (France, Greece, Turkey). Additionally, the "Class Consciousness" frame appears more frequently in social movement documents in cases like France, Italy, and Slovenia.

Differences among countries emerge in other thematic campaigns, where the "Human Rights and Fundamental Freedoms" frame prevails as a key frame in many contexts, supplemented by "Bodily Autonomy" and "Structural Violence" in select cases. Country-specific frames also surface, such as ecofeminism in Greece and labor market value debates in Spain and Denmark, showing the variety of socio-economic concerns linked to feminist activism.

Variations between document types reflect differing levels of radicalism, with social movement materials often articulating stronger anti-capitalist and intersectional critiques. This contrast is evident in cases like Spain, where parliamentary debates lean towards social citizenship, while social

movements push for structural changes. Additionally, coalition-building and intersectional feminism are essential themes, with feminist actors increasingly adopting cross-movement alliances and a commitment to radical change, except in cases like Denmark, where critiques remain less intersectional.

Further differences in framing styles include varying interpretations of gender, with some countries favoring binary views, while others adopt a more intersectional, mutually constitutive approach. The articulation of gender equality also shifts from anti-discrimination and feminist empowerment to transformative approaches, depending on the national context. Finally, emotions play a critical role in mobilization strategies, with patterns ranging from rational, fact-based language to empathy and frustration, often targeting anti-gender threats and state deficiencies. Notably, Greek activists politicize emotions, using affective expressions as a strategy to challenge conventional politics.

In summary, the analysis highlights the nuanced and diverse ways feminist movements frame and communicate their struggles, with the "Structural Violence" frame emerging as a shared foundation across contexts. These frames not only reflect the complex intersections of oppression and activism but also underscore the dynamic interplay between local and transnational feminist agendas. By examining how feminist and anti-gender actors articulate their positions, the findings provide a deeper understanding of the ideological, emotional, and strategic dimensions shaping contemporary gender politics, revealing both areas of convergence and sites of contestation.

2.3. Discourse Network Analysis

DNA is an alternative SNA technique that allows for the identification of advocacy coalitions based on actors' policy preferences. In this case, data has been pulled from selected newspapers, over a determined period of time, through a list of relevant keywords. The coding process has been articulated through the identification of policy statements in newspapers, and the coding of the date of the statement, name of the actor / organization, policy issue, and the actor's position towards the issue (positive or negative) in the software Discourse Network Analyzer. Data has then been analyzed with R. To visualize the results of the analysis, we have produced relevant maps and charts that account for: 1) the actors that intervened more frequently in newspapers and their characteristics (whether political parties or grassroots organizations); 2) the organizational dynamics underlying both feminist and anti-feminist networks; 3) the degree of internal cohesion of these networks and the topic that draw actors together; and 4) the topics that have attracted the most attention over time. Below we report the key findings of this research stream.

2.3.1. Key Findings

In the majority of the cases we detected a predominance of political parties among actors. We have also seen a predominant position for NGOs and advocacy groups. In most of the cases we see a significant presence of feminist and/or LGBTQI+ rights advocacy. While in a few cases (Poland, Slovenia, France), anti-feminist and anti-gender groups also represent key actors, in the rest of the cases right wing political parties appear to be the placeholders for anti-feminist and anti-gender positions. In some cases, we detected a surprising absence of self-defined anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations at the top of the list even though their influence in policy debates is recognized as significant in qualitative data collection and existing literature (Italy, Turkey). This finding might indicate either that the strength of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations is overestimated in these national contexts, or that these organizations pursue more of a kind of backdoor diplomacy to reach their objectives in the policy realm. It may also reveal the approach taken by certain major media outlets, who purposefully avoid giving these actors a platform or a voice. Finally, in some cases, there were relevant convergences in specific

policy positions as well as general policy statements among gender critical feminists and anti-gender actors.

The topics that appeared as more central across cases are generally connected to LGBTQ+ rights, gender-based violence, women's rights and empowerment. The most controversial issues, that is those that appear to have produced the greatest disagreement among actors, are found again in the field of LGBTQ+ rights (marriage, adoption, labor market, gender identity, surrogacy). Abortion also sparked intense debates. Another key controversial topic regards the concept and nature of family: these include promotion of motherhood and heterosexual families, same sex marriage, adoption rights, mandatory shared custody, and mediation. The degree of controversy surrounding these arguments, which include questions over who is eligible to start a family, demonstrates how vulnerable the rights that LGBTQI+ people have earned in this area. Another key controversial topic is gender-based violence: while there is general agreement on having a violence against women legislation in many countries there is high disagreement on the nature of such a legislation and the kinds of punishment and procedures of prosecution it shall involve.

Significantly, for concepts such as women's rights and empowerment and gender equality, there is little disagreement. These findings could indicate a broader degree of consensus on these themes. However, this seeming consensus does not always translate into a similar level of agreement when it comes to specific policy areas whereby such ideas can be realized. The palpable contrast between the two sets inspired some of the reports to reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea without the political intention to put it into practice.

In some cases, the analysis revealed a fragmented political field with significant crisscrossing debate fields (Denmark, Poland, Greece, Slovenia, Spain) showing varied agreements and lacking clear polarization. In other cases, polarized fields with clear advocacy divides have emerged (Italy, Turkey, France) revealing opposing communities on key concepts.

Furthermore, the maps reveal a clear discursive polarization, with feminist and pro-LGBTQI+ positions forming a distinct advocacy community, separate from anti-feminist and anti-gender positions. When organizations adopt a feminist stance in one policy debate, they are often consistent in supporting similar positions across other debates. Discursive affinities also emerge: labor unions, rights-based organizations, and other progressive movements tend to align with feminist positions, while religious leaderships, when vocal, frequently align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions.

2.4. Comparative Picture and Integration of Findings

The results from the three research streams—interviews, critical frame analysis (CFA), and discourse network analysis (DNA)—provide a multi-faceted understanding of contemporary feminist movements across the eight European countries included in the analysis. By synthesizing these findings, a comparative picture emerges, highlighting commonalities and divergences in the ways feminist activism navigates political landscapes, articulates frames, and engages with adversaries and allies. These comparative dimension will be further developed in the WP3.

2.4.1. Common Struggles and Shared Discourses

Across all three research streams, some key issues emerge as crucial: gender-based violence (GBV), reproductive rights, and LGBTQ+ rights. Furthermore, the structural violence frame identified in the CFA echoes the themes highlighted in interviews and DNA, where feminist activists consistently define GBV as a systemic issue rooted in patriarchy, capitalism, and other forms of oppression. Similarly, the

emphasis on intersectionality emerges as a unifying paradigm across diverse national contexts, although its application varies in scope and intensity.

Other central themes that emerged across all research streams concern the centrality of digital activism, the connection to transnational mobilizations like that of Ni Una Menos and the #MeToo, and the sustained focus on care work and economic inequalities.

2.4.2. National Specificities

While feminist movements share overarching themes, their strategies, organizational structures, and alliances vary significantly. For instance:

- *Organizational Diversity*: Movements in Italy, Spain, and Greece are predominantly grassroots and non-hierarchical, whereas Denmark demonstrates a more institutionalized feminist activism. This diversity is reflected in both the data collected through interviews and DNA.
- *Frames and Emotions*: Both interviews and CFA reveal distinct framing styles, with some countries like Greece incorporating ecofeminism and others emphasizing labor market inequalities (Spain, Denmark). Emotional strategies also vary, with Greek activists politicizing affective expressions to challenge the status quo, contrasting with more fact-based narratives in Denmark.
- *Polarization and Advocacy Coalitions*: DNA highlights differences in advocacy dynamics. Italy, France and Turkey show clearer polarization between feminist and anti-gender actors, while countries like Slovenia and Spain reveal fragmented political fields with more fluid alliances.

2.4.3. Coalitions and Alliances

The interplay between feminist and allied actors, such as LGBTQ+ groups, labor unions, and progressive organizations, is evident across all research streams. Interviews underscore the importance of these alliances in amplifying feminist voices, while DNA maps demonstrate the consistency of feminist stances across multiple policy debates. However, the degree of institutional support varies, with Denmark showcasing robust feminist affiliations within institutional actors, whereas Turkey and Poland highlight adversarial relations with closed political systems.

2.4.4. Challenges and Backlash

All research streams converge on the growing threat posed by anti-gender movements and conservative backlash, which significantly shape feminist strategies. This reactive dimension is particularly pronounced in contexts like Poland and Turkey, where feminist movements face significant barriers to proactive policymaking. The DNA findings further illuminate the strategic positioning of anti-gender actors, whose influence often extends beyond visible advocacy, operating through "backdoor diplomacy" or covert alignments.

2.4.5. Outcomes and Policy Impact

While feminist movements have achieved notable discursive shifts and cultural changes, especially in raising awareness of GBV, their policy impact remains uneven. Interviews reveal frustration with limited policy influence, particularly in restrictive political environments like Turkey. Yet, successes in legal reforms are evident in countries like Spain and Slovenia, demonstrating that feminist advocacy can yield tangible policy outcomes under favorable conditions.

2.5. Concluding remarks

The findings from interviews, CFA, and DNA collectively reveal a dynamic and resilient feminist movement landscape. Despite facing significant opposition, feminist movements across the eight

countries are leveraging intersectional frameworks, forming strategic alliances, and innovating their repertoires of action to navigate complex and often polarized political terrains. These movements not only resist authoritarianism and anti-gender backlash but also foster democratic innovations and cultural transformation, albeit with varying degrees of success depending on national contexts. Intra-feminist debates have been detected, particularly around surrogacy, trans rights and sex work, highlighting contentious gender politics as a common trait across the eight countries. The comparative analysis underscores the importance of understanding these movements as both locally grounded and transnationally connected, highlighting their potential to inspire progressive change in diverse socio-political environments.

In the following we present the extended reports of the three research streams. Each part presents an overall introduction to the research stream, a detailed examination of the method and the key findings.

3. Introduction to the research stream: interviews

Authors: Anastasia Barone and Giada Bonu Rosenkranz, SNS

3.1. Introduction

This section presents the results of the interview research stream. One of the FIERCE's goal is to explore and document the current phase of feminist mobilizations across Europe, with a particular focus on the diverse strategies, challenges, and innovations emerging from these movements. This phase of mobilization, which has gained momentum since the 2010s, has been marked by the rise of transnational feminist movements, such as Ni Una Menos and #MeToo, and the simultaneous escalation of conservative and far-right attacks on gender rights. By examining feminist movements in Italy, Denmark, France, Turkey, Greece, Poland, Slovenia, and Spain, this project aims to provide a comprehensive understanding of the ways feminist activism is reshaping political landscapes, fostering democratic innovation, and resisting growing authoritarianism.

A key component of the FIERCE project has been the collection and analysis of interviews with feminist activists and politicians, who have provided valuable insights into the strategies, discourses, and organizational models that define contemporary feminist movements. These interviews offer an in-depth perspective on the internal dynamics of feminist organizing, the external pressures posed by anti-gender movements, and the critical importance of intersectionality, care work, and digital activism in shaping feminist practices today.

This research stream of the FIERCE project is grounded in qualitative research, employing semi-structured interviews as the primary method for gathering in-depth insights into the experiences, strategies, and perspectives of feminist activists and organizations across Europe. This methodology was chosen to allow for a flexible yet systematic exploration of the key themes and issues shaping feminist mobilizations in different national contexts. The interview guide (see appendix), developed collectively by project partners, ensured consistency across cases while allowing for adaptation based on local specificities.

3.2. The method

Interviews were conducted with a diverse range of feminist activists, including members, founders, and directors of both formal organizations and informal networks, and institutional or political actors. The selection of interviewees was based on their active involvement in feminist mobilizations, with a focus on those engaged in campaigns addressing gender-based violence, reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, labor issues, and the broader struggle against patriarchy and neoliberalism. A purposive sampling

strategy was employed to ensure the inclusion of activists representing a variety of organizational forms, from grassroots collectives to more institutionalized NGOs.

In total, 240 interviews were conducted, each lasting between one and two hours. 163 interviews have been conducted with feminist activists (around 20 per country) and 69 with representatives of political parties and/or policy decision makers who support feminist initiatives (around 10 per country). Interviews were carried out either in person or online, depending on logistical constraints and the preferences of the interviewees. All interviews were recorded and transcribed with the participants' consent, ensuring adherence to ethical guidelines regarding privacy and confidentiality. There were no significant challenges in contacting feminist activists, and they were generally enthusiastic about participating in the research. They perceived it as an occasion to reflect on their activism experiences and contribute to the construction of knowledge about the current phase of feminist activism in Europe. In certain instances, the scarcity of time and the reduced availability of policy makers for activities outside of their primary policy work made it more challenging to contact them, necessitating more time-consuming networking efforts and research work.

The semi-structured nature of the interviews allowed for a flexible and conversational approach, encouraging participants to share their experiences and insights in their own terms while also ensuring that key themes were systematically addressed. The interview guide was organized around several thematic areas, designed to capture the multi-dimensional nature of feminist activism. These themes included:

- History and Ideology: Interviewees were asked about the history of their group or organization, the motivations behind its founding, and the personal and collective ideologies driving their activism. This allowed for an understanding of the long-term development of feminist movements in each country.
- Issues, Claims, and Frames: Interviewees discussed the specific issues their group focuses on, such as gender-based violence, reproductive rights, LGBTQ+ rights, and labor issues. This section also explored how activists frame these issues within broader struggles against patriarchy, neoliberalism, and anti-gender ideologies.
- Causes of the Problem: Participants were asked to reflect on who or what they see as responsible for the challenges they face, and how these problems are perpetuated. This section provided insights into activists' perceptions of power structures and the actors they confront, such as the state, far-right movements, and conservative institutions.
- Repertoire of Action: Interviewees were invited to discuss the forms of action their group engages in, such as protests, strikes, boycotts, or artistic performances. This section captured the diversity of tactics used in feminist mobilizations, highlighting both traditional and innovative forms of activism.
- Goals and Outcomes: Participants reflected on the successes and challenges of their activism, detailing the impact of their actions in various fields such as policy, education, media, and public discourse. This section provided a nuanced view of the effectiveness of feminist interventions across different contexts.
- Policy Influence and Institutional Engagement: Interviewees discussed their group's relationship with state institutions and policymakers, including successes and failures in influencing gender policies. This section highlighted the complexity of feminist activism's interaction with institutional politics, including opportunities and challenges for policy change.
- Allies and Networks: Participants were asked about their collaborations with other feminist organizations and movements, both domestic and transnational. This section focused on the alliances feminist groups form and the networks they build to strengthen their movements.

- Organizational Structure and Decision-Making: This section explored how feminist groups organize internally, including decision-making processes, the distribution of tasks, and the implementation of care practices. Interviewees shared their experiences with both hierarchical and non-hierarchical structures, reflecting the diversity of organizational models in contemporary feminist activism.
- Future Vision: Lastly, interviewees were asked about their future goals and their vision for a more just society. They also expressed their interest in participating in future FIERCE activities, particularly in joint political actions, discussions, and networking initiatives.

The interviews were transcribed and coded using a thematic analysis approach, allowing for the identification of recurring themes and patterns across the different cases. Key themes such as gender-based violence, intersectionality, care practices, and the impact of conservative backlash emerged from the analysis, providing a comprehensive understanding of the strategies and challenges faced by feminist movements in Europe. The transnational dimension of feminist activism, along with the role of digital and traditional media, were also central to the analysis.

The research adhered to strict ethical standards, ensuring the confidentiality and anonymity of all participants. Informed consent was obtained before each interview, and participants were given the option to withdraw at any point. The project also ensured that sensitive topics, such as experiences of violence or discrimination, were approached with care, and interviewees were provided with support resources where necessary.

This introduction outlines the core themes that emerged from these interviews and provides a context for understanding the broader political and social environments in which feminist movements are operating. The findings highlight not only the commonalities across different national contexts, such as the centrality of gender-based violence and reproductive rights, but also the unique challenges faced by activists in specific countries, shaped by local political structures, economic conditions, and cultural frameworks. In doing so, the project sheds light on the multifaceted nature of feminist activism in Europe, emphasizing its role in confronting both enduring and emerging forms of oppression.

By focusing on the strategies and practices of feminist movements in a range of European countries, the FIERCE project contributes to a growing body of scholarship on transnational activism, social movement theory, and feminist democratic innovations. It provides an opportunity to reflect on how feminist movements are responding to the complex intersections of patriarchy, neoliberalism, and authoritarianism, and how they are pioneering new forms of resistance and solidarity in the process. The interviews not only document the rich diversity of feminist activism but also offer theoretical insights into the future directions of feminist struggles in Europe and beyond.

3.3. Key findings

Interviews with feminist activists and politicians who support feminist initiatives have constituted a fundamental source of knowledge for a more profound comprehension of the contemporary phase of feminist movements in Europe. Indeed, since the 2010s, a new wave of mobilization has emerged. This decade has been identified by interviewees in all countries under examination as marking a significant shift with respect to the past. This was largely driven by the rise of the Ni Una Menos movement in Argentina and the global #MeToo mobilization. The transnational dimension was identified as a significant factor influencing the development of movements at the national level by participants in all countries. It is noteworthy that participants also identified the increased strength of right-wing, far-right, and anti-gender actors as a key factor in the rise of the new wave of mobilization. These actors have posed a significant threat to existing gender policies, contracting women's and LGBTQ+ rights, and increasing the level of discrimination. In some instances, specific threats served as the impetus for the emergence of this new cycle. For instance, the (unsuccessful) attempt to restrict the right to abortion in

Spain and the even more stringent developments that unfolded in Poland, where anti-abortion actors relentlessly advocated for the further tightening of the already limited right to abortion in the country. While transnational diffusion and the existence of significant threats have thus played a crucial role, the interviews conducted for this study also demonstrated that the new feminist uprising did not emerge in a vacuum. Rather, as activists underlined in all countries, previously existing networks, groups, and mobilizations have represented the backdrop upon which the new phases have been built in all cases. In some countries, such as Greece, Spain, and Italy, the interviewees highlight that the new mobilization is particularly rooted in anti-austerity protests. In general, previous women's and feminist mobilizations appear to be relevant for contemporary activism.

The analysis indicates that the advent of the new wave of feminist mobilization can be attributed to the confluence of specific political opportunity structures, particularly in view of the challenges posed by far-right actors, continuities with preceding cycles of mobilization, and innovations introduced by the current cycle.

Since the 2010s, a central concern for feminist movements across Europe has been the issue of gender-based violence (GBV). This has emerged as a central and pervasive topic in all of the cases that have been subjected to analysis. In most cases, activists reported to us that sexual and domestic violence have constituted the primary area of contention in their countries, together with institutional, economic, and medical violence. The focus of movements on this issue has been accompanied by heightened institutional attention, exemplified by the implementation of the Istanbul Convention and several local and global laws addressing gender-based violence. As it emerged in the cases of Italy, Spain, Poland, and France, feminist movements in this phase have started framing their fight against gender-based violence as part of a broader struggle against patriarchy. The interviewees view this approach as a way to frame oppression as structural and systemic, aiming to challenge the underlying patriarchal and sexist cultures and structures.

While GBV represents the core topic addressed by movements, reproductive rights remain a central and contested issue, especially the right to abortion, which is constantly threatened by anti-choice actors. As mentioned above, in Poland, the fight for the legalization of abortion has been the starting point for the new cycle of mobilization. A similar development unfolded in Spain when activists mobilized against a legislative proposal that sought to restrict the right to abortion. However, the analysis conducted in Italy, Slovenia and Turkey shows that even when abortion is legally protected, informal obstacles to abortion, such as conscience objection and medical violence and systemic neglect in public hospital services, increased over the past decade. While in most countries the fight for the right to abortion has been mainly in defense of existing legal frameworks and countering attempts by far-right and anti-choice actors, Denmark represents a different case, in which debates about abortion have emerged in light of a proposal to extend existing regulations and making abortion possible after the 12th week of pregnancy. Furthermore, while abortion represents a key topic of struggle, the field of fights for sexual and reproductive rights appears to be much broader, including the right to healthcare for all, access to hormonal contraception, and medically assisted reproduction.

LGBTQ+ rights also have come to constitute a key field of intervention for feminist movements in Europe. In almost all the cases we have analyzed the alliance between feminist and LGBTQ collectives represents a key aspect in the recent wave of mobilization. In general, all issues tackled by feminist movements, including gender-based violence and sexual and reproductive health claim recognition, protection and access for women and LGBTQ+ people. In some cases, specific campaigns and intervention have unfolded during the last decade: in Slovenia, for example, same-sex marriage was legalized in 2022. However, prior to this, strong anti-gender opposition to marriage equality contributed to the formation of a strong coalition of LGBT and feminist actors in the struggle to achieve marriage

equality for all. Other debates have revolved around the legalization and recognition of gender identity. A most pressing issue in this field is represented by hate crime and hate speech and more generally the discrimination faced by LGBTQ+ people.

A key aspect of contemporary feminist movements in Europe is constituted by a renewed attention to economic inequalities, labor and care work. This is partly also the result of the increased relevance of an anti-capitalist approach within feminism, as it was highlighted especially in the cases of Italy, Spain, France, and Poland. In some countries, such as Spain and Turkey, activists reported that the issue of unpaid labour and economic inequalities has become a key field of intervention in mainstream discourses. In Spain, in particular, this has emerged thanks to the work of migrant domestic workers organizations. In general, care work and reproductive labor have been at the center of the global feminist strikes, which have been particularly relevant in some European countries such as Italy, France, and Spain. The gender-pay gap emerged as more central in Denmark.

Another important element characterizing the current phase of feminist movements in Europe is the intersectional perspective, which has become a critical paradigm in feminist activism, notably in Spain, France, Turkey, Italy, and Slovenia, addressing the overlapping and intersecting nature of various forms of oppression. Some interviewees also mentioned that the intersectional approach sometimes has constituted one of the crucial terrain of conflicts among different sectors of and generations within feminist circles. This is particularly the case in France, where tension has arisen regarding the intersectional perspective between a new generation of activists and traditional universalistic approaches. Denmark represents once again a different case, since an intersectional approach does not seem central to contemporary feminist discourses.

A central aspect for activists in most of the countries is the necessity to respond to the conservative backlash and to anti-gender movements and policies. This was especially relevant in the cases of Slovenia, Turkey, France, and Poland. In some cases, like Poland, this has also raised questions about the almost exclusively reactive nature of feminist politics. In fact, the energy of feminist movements has been redirected in response to anti-gender attacks, which has hindered their capacity to cultivate proactive practices and prefigurative politics that extend beyond mere resistance.

In examining the feminist movements in the countries under scrutiny, differences emerged in terms of the organizational structures. In some cases, the movement has a largely informal and non-hierarchical structure. This is the case for Italy, Spain and Greece. In other countries, movements tend to be more institutionalized NGOs, such as in Denmark. In general, in most cases the movement presents a multifaceted nature in terms of organizational forms, with more grassroots groups coexisting with associations and professional organizations and institutional actors like political parties.

A central feature emerging in the analysis of organizational models concerns the implementation of care. In some cases, such as for example Italy, Turkey and Greece, activists explicitly referred to the implementation of care practices within collectives, groups, assemblies and meetings. In some cases, such as in the case of Turkey, these practices also represent a response to a sense of overall precarity that collectivities experience in the context of conservative backlash. The degree of repression and the risk that activists have to face require particular attention to care practices.

Regarding the relationship between movement actors and the institutional sphere, the activists we interviewed reported to generally have a complex relationship with politicians and political actors. Some exceptions exist, for example in Denmark, where there is a stronger feminist affiliation among some institutional actors, demonstrating support for feminist initiatives. Conversely, in other countries, this association is more nuanced or completely absent, indicating a diversity of institutional responses to feminist activism. In some cases, a sense of distrust prevails despite close ideological positioning

between grassroots activists and feminist within the institutions. This is the case for example in Italy and Spain.

As for the repertoires of action adopted by the movements, in most cases the participants reported that the main forms of intervention are protest, demonstrations and more broadly the occupation of the public space with visible actions. In this field, however, participants highlighted the innovative use of performances, as part of a new repertoire. Performances are used to channel the movement's message through embodied artistic intervention in the streets. This is the case in Italy where street performances have become prominent, but also in Greece and Slovenia, where artistic forms of expression have acquired increased relevance within the movement and festivals, parties and workshops have come to side with traditional protest and demonstrations. As the French case shows this is also a way to display joy, as a measure to counter the backlash. The use of emotions is prominent in communication strategies, although often used cautiously, as seen in Slovenia, where activists reflect on a balance between the use of an emotional language and the ability to stick to the facts, differing in this regard from the use of emotions generally made by anti-gender movements. Another relevant aspect regarding the relationship between innovative repertoires of action and the use of emotions concerns mourning as a repertoire: in Italy and to some extent, Turkey, participants highlighted the relevance of funerals and memorials aimed at remembering women and trans women that were murdered.

A key tool in the movements' repertoire is represented by forms of direct social action, mutualistic support, community work and all those forms of intervention that imply direct and peer-to-peer support. Individual accompaniments, especially in the health sectors, emerge as central in Italy and France, as a way to resist the obstacles that a person may encounter when faced with health and medical institutions.

Another aspect that emerged as central is the role of education, training and knowledge production within feminist movements. This appeared as central in all the countries we analyzed. Activists may act as experts on feminist issues and participate in training with other experts or public officials, as it happens in Slovenia. In other cases, forms of knowledge production are used to be spread to a wider public. In Turkey this has materialized in the diffusion of booklets about gender-based violence, workshops and training. In Italy this is often the case for the spreading of information regarding access to health institutions for abortion.

Furthermore, the digital space has emerged as a crucial arena for feminist activism, particularly in France, Greece, Italy, Turkey, and Spain. The case of Denmark has raised questions on the possibility that the role of digital media may be overstated in academic literature, since the interviews indicated that more traditional tools such as protests and petitions are more generally mentioned by the participants rather than online actions. Furthermore, the case of Slovenia also points at the role of traditional media, such as television, newspapers and the radio, which continue to play an influential role.

When asked about their movements' outcomes, most participants in all countries pointed at the discursive shifts and cultural change they obtained, especially in the field of GBV. A broader awareness of the issue is recognized as having increased thanks to movements initiatives, sometimes including changes in the language and framing, as in the case of the term femicide. In Italy, for example, while no particular political or institutional outcome was underlined by activists, the interviewees reported that they believed society had changed thanks to feminist initiatives.

As for the policy and institutional level, in some cases activists express strong frustration with the closedness of the political system, impermeable to their claims. This was especially the case in Turkey, where a strong setback has taken place with the withdrawal from the Istanbul Convention. In other cases, despite the often complex mechanism for activists to exert an influence at the policy level,

significant legal and policy changes were highlighted as well. In Greece, for example, important institutional outcomes have been obtained under the Syriza government, including the legal recognition of gender identity. In Slovenia, during the last decades, feminist actions and campaigns secured key legal and institutional changes in the field of sexual and reproductive health, violence and migrant domestic workers labor conditions. In Spain, key achievements have been secured in the field of gender-based violence, sexual and reproductive rights and trans rights. Furthermore, key national debates concerning care work have been sparked by feminist discourses and actions. In the case of Denmark, interviewees remarked that the last decades, especially thanks to the recent feminist mobilizations, opened up an unprecedented political opportunity for gender policies to be advanced, despite the challenges posed by counter-movements. On the side of politicians and policymakers they recognized, almost in all countries, that the rise of the massive phase of feminist mobilizations empowered their actions within parties and institutions.

3.4. Conclusion

The interviews conducted for the FIERCE project provide a valuable and in-depth understanding of feminist movements across Europe. The data underscores the adaptability and resilience of these movements in the face of diverse political, social, and economic challenges. As feminist movements continue to confront deeply entrenched patriarchal structures and respond to neoliberal policies, they also serve as incubators for democratic innovation. Their approaches to activism—particularly in the arenas of intersectionality, care work, and gender-based violence—reveal a dynamic and multifaceted strategy for social change that encompasses both grassroots actions and formal institutional engagement.

A key conclusion from this research is the pivotal role of feminist movements in shaping not just gender policies but also broader societal transformations. By addressing systemic inequalities and challenging reactionary forces, these movements have been instrumental in resisting the conservative backlash observed in many European contexts. The interviews highlighted how feminist activists are actively developing innovative repertoires of action, often blending traditional forms of protest with new, creative, and digital methods.

The findings offer rich insights into feminist movements across Europe, contributing significantly to existing theoretical frameworks on social movements, democratic innovations, and intersectionality. These movements have not only responded to immediate political and social threats, such as the rise of far-right and anti-gender actors, but have also generated innovative democratic practices and strategies that challenge traditional political structures.

One of the central theoretical implications of the findings is the role of feminist movements as agents of democratic innovation, especially in times of conservative backlash (Caravantes & Lombardo, 2023; della Porta, 2020; della Porta & Felicetti, 2022; Fominaya, 2022). Scholars such as Nancy Fraser (2013) have discussed how feminist movements often operate at the intersection of social justice and democratic revitalization, advocating for deeper forms of participation and inclusion. The findings from the FIERCE project align with Fraser's argument that feminist activism is not only a fight for gender equality but also a broader struggle for social justice in a neoliberal world. The movements' responses to austerity, patriarchy, and the far-right reveal how they are reshaping the boundaries of democratic participation through grassroots actions, intersectional policies, and care-based organizing models (Delphy & Leonard, 1980). The analysis of how feminist movements frame care as a political practice, contributes to the literature on deliberative democracy (Mansbridge, 1999), which emphasizes dialogue and inclusive decision-making as central to democratic life (della Porta, 2020).

The attention to care practices within organizational models, especially in Italy, Turkey, and Greece, reflects these deliberative principles, offering a more horizontal and inclusive approach to decision-

making that centers marginalized voices (Marx Ferree & Martin, 1995; Della Porta & Lavizzari, 2022; Dengler & Lang, 2022; Pulcini, 2017; Tronto, 1987). The findings suggest that care, both as a practice and as a principle of organizing, challenges the individualistic and competitive logics of neoliberalism (Tronto, 2013). Care within feminist collectives, particularly in contexts of heightened repression and precarity, as seen in Turkey, represents a radical form of political organizing that foregrounds the vulnerability of individuals and the collective. Scholars such as Joan Tronto (2013) have argued that the politics of care offers a feminist critique of the patriarchal and neoliberal structures that dominate contemporary society. In this sense, the integration of care into feminist activism, as both an ethical and organizational principle, expands the literature on feminist ethics and provides practical models for resistance in hostile political environments.

A key theoretical implication of the findings lies in its examination of feminist responses to anti-gender mobilizations, a growing phenomenon across Europe that seeks to roll back gender equality gains (Graff & Korolczuk, 2022; Kuhar & Paternotte, 2017; Lavizzari, 2019; Roggeband & Krizsán, 2024). These anti-gender movements, often aligned with far-right populism and conservative actors, challenge feminist efforts on multiple fronts, from reproductive rights to LGBTQ+ recognition. Scholars such as Paternotte and Kuhar (2018) have analyzed the rise of these anti-gender campaigns, describing them as a form of backlash politics that seeks to undermine gender justice by mobilizing against what they label "gender ideology." The FIERCE findings underscore the resilience and adaptability of feminist movements in confronting this backlash. In countries like Poland, Italy, and France, feminist activists have responded to these challenges with a combination of grassroots mobilizations, transnational solidarity networks, and legal advocacy. The findings reveal how feminist movements have used cross-border alliances to resist these reactionary forces, sharing strategies, framing the backlash as a broader attack on democracy, and pushing back through both street protests and institutional lobbying. This connects to broader discussions in the literature on how feminist movements evolve in the face of political opportunity structures (Kitschelt, 1986), as they strategically engage with and resist state actors, far-right parties, and religious institutions. The FIERCE project contributes to this scholarship by showing that while anti-gender movements seek to reverse feminist gains, they often also act as a catalyst for feminist organizing, energizing feminist responses and reinforcing the importance of intersectional and care-based activism as forms of resistance to authoritarianism and neoliberalism (Smrdelj and Kuhar, forthcoming).

Moreover, as our analysis shows, feminist activism has played a critical role in transnational diffusion, particularly through digital media. Keck and Sikkink's (1998) theory of transnational advocacy networks helps explain how feminist movements leverage global platforms to share strategies and build solidarity across borders. The influence of the #MeToo movement and Ni Una Menos is emblematic of this transnational diffusion, revealing how global feminist issues are localized in national contexts (Hesse-Biber, 2012). Social media platforms, in particular, serve as spaces where feminist ideas are circulated, translated, and adapted to local struggles, in line with Tarrow's (2005) work on the diffusion of protest movements. While the project's findings acknowledge that in some countries, like Denmark, traditional media still plays a dominant role, the broader picture illustrates how digital activism has transformed the way feminist movements communicate, mobilize, and coordinate across borders.

This transnationalism is further supported by the emergence of intersectionality as a critical framework in contemporary feminist activism (Bassel & Emejulu, 2014; Bonu Rosenkranz, 2024; Calderaro & Lépinard, 2021). First conceptualized by Kimberlé Crenshaw (1989), intersectionality highlights how different forms of oppression—such as race, class, and gender—intersect to shape the experiences of marginalized groups. The FIERCE project demonstrates how this framework has become central to feminist movements, particularly in countries like Spain, France, and Italy, where activists are

increasingly using intersectional approaches to address systemic inequalities. The internal debates within feminist circles, particularly in France, regarding intersectionality versus more traditional universalist approaches, reflect broader tensions identified by scholars such as Lélia Gonzalez (1988) and Patricia Hill Collins (2000), who emphasize that feminist movements must continuously navigate these internal conflicts to remain inclusive and representative of diverse identities.

Innovative repertoires of action, another key theoretical implication, also emerge strongly from our analysis. Scholars such as Charles Tilly (2006) have long discussed how movements adopt diverse forms of protest and action, and the feminist movements analyzed here exemplify this in new and creative ways. Performances, street art, and embodied actions, as seen in Italy, Greece, and Slovenia, represent a shift towards a more aestheticized form of protest (Butler, 2015). These actions are not merely symbolic; they channel emotions, memory, and collective identity into public spaces, creating new forms of visibility and engagement. Judith Butler's (2015) concept of performative assembly is relevant here, as these feminist movements demonstrate how bodily presence in public space becomes an act of resistance, countering the increasing invisibility and silencing of marginalized groups. The use of mourning and memorials, as highlighted in Turkey and Italy, further connects to the literature on mourning as protest (Brown & Hirsch, 2013), showing how grief and loss can be transformed into political action.

Finally, the digital space emerges as a crucial arena for feminist activism, reinforcing the arguments made by scholars such as Saskia Sassen (2014) and Jodi Dean (2010) about the role of digital technologies in shaping political movements. Feminist activists use online platforms not only to raise awareness but also to create alternative spaces for deliberation, solidarity, and collective action (Mattoni, 2016; Pavan, 2014; Pavan & Mainardi, 2018). The findings from the interviews, particularly the emphasis on digital activism in countries like France, Greece, and Spain, suggest that these platforms play a key role in sustaining activism across borders, offering tools for education, communication, and rapid mobilization.

In conclusion, these findings underscore the vital role of feminist movements in revitalizing democracy in Europe. By addressing systemic issues, advocating for comprehensive legal reforms, and fostering inclusive and intersectional approaches, these movements are crucial in promoting gender equality and social justice. The lessons learned from the diverse experiences of feminist activists across Europe highlight the resilience and determination of these movements. They demonstrate the ongoing fight for a more inclusive society and underscore the need for sustained support and recognition of feminist struggles in the quest for justice and equality.

References

- Bassel, L., & Emejulu, A. (2014). Solidarity under Austerity: Intersectionality in France and the United Kingdom. *Politics & Gender*, *10*(1), 130–136. <https://doi.org/10.1017/S1743923X13000597>
- Bonu Rosenkranz, G. (2024). Intersectionality and feminist movements from a global perspective. *Sociology Compass*, *18*(5), e13211. <https://doi.org/10.1111/soc4.13211>
- Calderaro, C., & Lépinard, É. (2021). Intersectionality as a new feeling rule for young feminists: Race and feminist relations in France and Switzerland. *European Journal of Women's Studies*, *28*(3), 387–404. <https://doi.org/10.1177/13505068211029687>
- Caravantes, P., & Lombardo, E. (2023). Feminist democratic innovations in policy and politics. *Policy & Politics*, *XX*(XX), 1–23. <https://doi.org/10.1332/03055736Y2023D000000009>
- della Porta, D. (2020). *How Social Movements Can Save Democracy: Democratic Innovations from Below*. John Wiley & Sons.
- della Porta, D., & Felicetti, A. (2022). Innovating Democracy Against Democratic Stress in Europe: Social Movements and Democratic Experiments. *Representation*, *58*(1), 67–84. <https://doi.org/10.1080/00344893.2019.1624600>
- Della Porta, D., & Lavizzari, A. (n.d.). Framing health and care: Legacies and innovation during the pandemic. *Social Movement Studies*, *0*(0), 1–18. <https://doi.org/10.1080/14742837.2022.2134109>
- Delphy, C., & Leonard, D. (1980). A Materialist Feminism is Possible. *Feminist Review*, *4*(1), 79–105. <https://doi.org/10.1057/fr.1980.8>

- Dengler, C., & Lang, M. (2022). Commoning Care: Feminist Degrowth Visions for a Socio-Ecological Transformation. *Feminist Economics*, 28(1), 1–28. <https://doi.org/10.1080/13545701.2021.1942511>
- Fominaya, C. F. (2022). Reconceptualizing Democratic Innovation: “Democratic Innovation Repertoires” and their Impact Within and Beyond Social Movements. *Democratic Theory*, 9(2), 78–100. <https://doi.org/10.3167/dt.2022.090205>
- Gago, V. (2020). *Feminist International: How to Change Everything*. Verso Books.
- Graff, A., & Korolczuk, E. (2022). *Anti-Gender Politics in the Populist Moment*. Taylor & Francis. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781003133520>
- Hesse-Bibier, S. N. (2012). *The Handbook of Feminist Research. Theory and Praxis*. SAGE.
- Kaitlynn Mendes, Jessica Ringrose, & Jessalynn Keller. (2018). #MeToo and the promise and pitfalls of challenging rape culture through digital feminist activism. <https://journals.sagepub.com/doi/full/10.1177/1350506818765318>
- Kuhar, R., & Paternotte, D. (2017). *Anti-Gender Campaigns in Europe: Mobilizing against Equality*. Rowman & Littlefield.
- Lavizzari, A. (2019). *Protesting Gender: The LGBTIQ Movement and its Opponents in Italy*. Routledge.
- Marx Ferree, M., & Martin, P. Y. (1995). *Feminist Organizations*. Temple University Press.
- Mattoni, A. (2016). *Media Practices and Protest Politics: How Precarious Workers Mobilise*. Routledge. <https://doi.org/10.4324/9781315594521>
- Pavan, E. (2014). Embedding Digital Communications Within Collective Action Networks: A Multidimensional Network Approach. *Mobilization: An International Quarterly*, 19(4), 441–455. <https://doi.org/10.17813/maiq.19.4.w24rl524u074126k>
- Pavan, E., & Mainardi, A. (2018). Striking, marching, tweeting: Studying how online networks change together with movements. *Partecipazione e Conflitto*, 11, 394–422. <https://doi.org/10.1285/i20356609v11i2p394>
- Pulcini, E. (2017). What Emotions Motivate Care? *Emotion Review*, 9(1), 64–71. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1754073915615429>
- Roggeband, C., & Krizsán, A. (2024). The Violent Implications of Opposition to the Istanbul Convention. *Societies*, 14(6), Article 6. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc14060092>
- Tronto, J. C. (1987). Beyond Gender Difference to a Theory of Care. *Signs: Journal of Women in Culture and Society*, 12(4), 644–663. <https://doi.org/10.1086/494360>

Appendix: semi-structured interviews guide

For reasons of convenience, in all following questions we use the term “group”, regardless of whether you represent / answer for an informal group / network or a formal organization.

The following interview will last approximately between one and two hours.

Please note that at the end of the interview, there will be shared questions about activists' interest to participate in a future FIERCE activity.

<u>Theme-Objective</u>	<u>Opening question</u>	<u>Prompts</u>
<u>History & Ideology</u>	Can you tell us a bit about the history of your group? How was it established? What were the organizers' goals?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How did people come together? How the group developed? • Can you also talk about your personal involvement and your motivations?
<u>Issues, claims and frames</u>	Can you tell us about the issues that you focus on? Which issues would you say are your main focus?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (if the interviewee names certain issues, others can be prompted from the list. The list can be adopted / shortened / prolonged depending on the context) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Gender terminology & Gender equality ○ Labor market ○ Health and reproductive rights ○ LGBTQI+ rights ○ Gender based violence, domestic violence ○ Migration • (For each) How do you see the existing situation? What do you think is the problem? • (For each) What do you think should be done / should change to resolve the problem? • if you use concepts such as intersectionality, care, commons, can you tell us what you mean by them?
<u>Causes of the problem</u>	Who do you think are responsible for this state of affairs? Who do you find yourself confronting in your advocacy?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What is the role they play in creating this problem? • How do you think they are able to create this problem? • What do you think should be the action taken against them?
<u>Repertoire of action</u>	In the last five years, which forms of action and/or campaigns has your group engaged in repeatedly? Can you list up five groups, networks or campaigns dealing with gender rights with which your group interacts most intensively?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • They can include, but not limited to: petition, demonstration, strike, boycott of certain products, blockade, occupation of buildings, civil disobedience, artistic/cultural performances • (For each) Can you tell us about these campaigns?
<u>Goals and outcomes</u>	What results do you think your group has achieved with respect to the goals and claims it brings forward?	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Did the strategies and tactics have been effective? • Which improvements (or not) your action produced?

		<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Can you detailed which fields have been affected most (education, culture, policy, institutions, media...)?
<u>Policy influence</u>	<p>How does your group relate to state institutions? Can you tell us about the outcomes of these relations?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What were some of the policies you want(ed) to influence? • What are some of the results you have achieved with your campaigns? And failed?
<u>Allies</u>	<p>Which actors, organizations do you interact with most in your campaigns and activities? Can you tell us about your collaborations?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • (Allies to be prompted) <ul style="list-style-type: none"> ○ Domestic allies ○ Transnational allies • How do you usually work together? Can you give examples? • Does your group take part in any networks or campaigns dealing with feminist ? • In which feminist campaigns/protest events did your group (not you personally) participate in? • Do you have connections with other feminist movements in other countries? • How do you develop these networks? What would be most useful to you? Networking meetings? Learning about history of feminist movements? Strategies to counter those opposed to gender rights? Legal knowledge? Other ideas?
<u>Organizational structure</u>	<p>Can you tell us a bit about the day-to-day work in the organization in terms of who does the work; how campaign, demonstration preparations take place; how the information dissemination is organized?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How is the work distributed? Who does most of the work? • Who takes the most important decisions in the every-day practice of your group? Is there a hierarchical structure or you engage with assembly/thematic groups? • Is it possible to become a member of your group? • Which kind of members does your group have? • How many members do voluntary (unpaid) work for your group on a regular basis? • Who is involved in maintaining the webpage, social media accounts and the distribution of information? How regularly is this done? • How are campaigns initiated, planned, and organized? • How are resources for the work generated? Which are sources of funds for your group? (Members' dues / contributions, Funds and financing of specific projects from

		<p>governments, Non governmental funds, Sale of goods / services / rents, Other)</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What do you think are your strengths? Weaknesses?
<u>Decision making- process</u>	<p>Do members of your group regularly meet in an assembly / open meeting in order to make decisions?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • How frequently are such assemblies held? Who takes decisions in these assemblies? (only delegates, members of the group, whoever wants to participate, others) • How many people generally participate in these assemblies? • Who proposes the agenda? (president / leader / secretary, the executive committee or similar body, the assembly / open meeting, a small committee which represents different groups of the membership, other) • How does the assembly usually make decisions?
<u>Future</u>	<p>What do you envisage for the future?</p>	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • What are your goals? What kind of a society do you want in the future? • What are your plans for achieving them?

To conclude, we propose some questions about the availability to be involved in future FIERCE activity:

- Would you be willing to participate in a space of discussion and joint political action organised by the FIERCE project with some of the abovementioned actors (consisting of three Labs), in order to establish alliances, examine the challenges you are facing and think about possible joint initiatives? Why?
- Which groups would you be willing to participate in this initiative with (thinking in particular of potential intersectional and cross-movement alliances)? With which stakeholders you would not be willing to participate? Why?
- Would you be open to work with institutional stakeholders? At what level (national, regional, local)?
- What topics would you be interested in addressing in a space like this?

4. Introduction to the research stream: CFA

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Critical frame analysis (CFA) was applied to the analysis of documents about and by anti-gender and anti-feminist actors (WP1) as well as feminist movements (WP2). We followed the same CFA guide for both WPs. The stated aim of the analysis was to identify how gender and gender categories are framed, used, disseminated and widely communicated. This included analysis of major and minor frames within the five thematic areas (labour market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, gender-based violence) as well as intersectional patterns and emotions. We also paid particular attention to potential policy impact or policy influence, as these were accounted for in the analyzed documents. Our basic unit of analysis was campaigns, conceptualized as a long-lasting political process that includes a policy dimension (e.g., a legislative proposal) as well as an activist dimension (e.g., mobilization supporting or opposing policy change). With CFA, we analyzed the documents emerging in the context of such a campaign. Each partner suggested three salient campaigns covering their national case, within the 2010-2023 time frame. Based on an overview of all the suggested campaigns, we selected one campaign from each national case focusing on the thematic area of LGBTQ+ rights, for WP1, and gender-based violence (GBV), for WP2, due to the saliency of these two themes across all country cases. The selection of the second campaign to be coded was decided upon by each partner. More information on the rationale behind the choices of the specific campaigns for each country case can be found in the CFA country reports. For WP2, the following selection of campaigns was made:

Country	Campaign 1	Campaign 2
France	GBV	LGBTQI+
Greece	GBV	LGBTQI+
Denmark	GBV	Labour market (equal pay)
Italy	GBV	Education
Spain	GBV	Labour market (care work)
Turkey	GBV	Multi-issue
Poland	GBV	Reproductive rights
Slovenia	GBV/Reproductive rights	LGBTQI+

Table 1 Overview of campaign selection per country

A minimum of five parliamentary debate interventions (i.e., political texts) and ten documents from social movement actors (i.e., activist texts) per campaign were coded per WP per country.

CFA guidelines were prepared and discussed among the task and work package leaders and disseminated to all partners. CFA is a text analysis approach which focuses on how political and social issues are problematized by analyzing articulations of problems and solutions and their normative underpinnings. Building on social movement literature as well as policy analysis, it is used to analyze policy proposals as well as social movement mobilization and demands. A frame can be defined as an “organizing principle that transforms fragmentary or incidental information into a structured and meaningful problem, in which a solution is implicitly or explicitly included” (Verloo, 2005: 20). Thus, frames are considered frameworks of understanding, which help us make sense of reality and structure meaning, through processes of social interaction (in which the frames are defined). CFA traditionally focuses on three main elements of texts: **diagnosis** (i.e., the way in which problems are represented and defined in the text or by an actor), **prognosis** (i.e., the way in which solutions to the problems are proposed), and **voice** (i.e., **actors** producing the frames as well as the ones attributed authority or given standing in the texts) (Dombos et al., 2012; Ferree et al., 2002).

The CFA guidelines laid out the FIERCE approach to CFA which attends to: 1) the *frame content*, i.e., diagnostic and prognostic codes to identify and map frames, as well as overall interpretation codes to register understandings of gender, emotions, and intersectional dimensions related to the frames; and 2) *frame contextualization*, allowing us to bridge CFA with results from discourse network analysis and interviews to make a comprehensive analysis of the policy process in WP3. Please see the detailed account of the FIERCE approach to CFA in the codebook below (Appendix A). The coding integrated both open and closed codes. The latter were integrated in the code system as predefined sub-codes (with an additional, open 'other' option in each case). Codes were illustrated with segments from the original texts. Based on the FIERCE literature reviews, predefined frames were identified and included in the CFA guidelines, with descriptions of each frame, as well as in the code system, as closed codes (please see Appendix B for the list of predefined frames for WP2). Other frames emerging from the empirical material were included in the coding as open codes. Frames and problem statements were weighted as major, minor, or marginal, and code sets were established in the software to create links between different codes making up frames (code marker combinations, e.g., problem statement-active actor-passive actor-underlying norm).

The coding was carried out with the use of MAXQDA. The CFA coders of the country teams were introduced to the approach at a physical meeting in May 2023, and they were provided with tailored video tutorials for the use of the software and the code system (based on the codebook). Code system files were prepared and shared with all partners, and online Q&A sessions were organized to resolve technical doubts related to the use of the software. To ensure intercoder reliability, the codebook was tested by the country teams; a hybrid CFA workshop was carried out; and online coder community sessions were celebrated regularly throughout the coding period. This process included three test codings, where all coders coded the same document and compared the results, as well as continuous discussions and alignments of the coding approach and code system. The first coder community sessions resulted in slight adjustments or clarifications of the coding approach, summarized in a short, additional set of guidelines, shared with all partners. This included, e.g., emphasizing that coders should seek to strike a balance between using the predefined codes whenever possible without losing sight of the need to add additional codes ('bottom-up coding') to account for important nuances and national specificities, e.g.

The coding resulted in national summary reports; the guidelines for the summary reports were discussed among the coders of the national teams and presented to the entire consortium for input. The final version of the guidelines included sections on: 1) Campaign and document selection as well as contextualization (the policy/mobilization process); 2) overview of frames; 3) explanation of code marker combinations; 4) summary of overall interpretation codes; 5) tentative analysis; and 6) comparison between frames of WP1 and WP2 documents. The summary reports were reviewed by the task leader, with two rounds of revisions, including alignment of frames (to ensure consistency across country cases in terms of the identification of frames). The main findings of the national CFA summary reports are accounted for in the following section.

4.1. Key findings

The coding of the frames shows a series of patterns across the country cases, emphasizing both similarities and differences between them. For what concerns the gender-based violence (GBV) campaigns, selected across all country cases, the 'Structural violence' frame is clearly the most

significant one among the documents by feminist actors (see table 2 below).¹ This shows how a structural understanding of gender-based violence has gained prominence in recent years in a development driven mainly by social movement actors. A variety of other frames are also important in relation to the GBV campaigns but to a much lesser extent. This is the case of the Intersectional Frame, 'Class consciousness'²; the Political-economic Frame, 'Contested gender equality'³; the Health and Reproductive Rights Frame, 'Bodily autonomy'⁴; and the GBV frame, 'Violence as universal'.⁵ This clearly reflects how the theme of GBV is multidimensional in its dominant articulation.

Considering the differences between the types of documents coded (parliamentary debate interventions and social movement documents), we can see that there is more diversity of frames in the social movement documents (a larger number of different frames are present in the material). The Intersectional Frames stand out in this regard: 'Racism and nationalism' is only articulated as a major frame in social movement documents (France, Greece, Turkey) and the same is the case for 'LGBTQ+ rights' (Turkey). Similarly, there is a stronger weight on 'Class consciousness' as a major frame in social movement documents (France, Italy, Slovenia) as compared to parliamentary debates (Italy).

¹ Present in all country cases (eight in total); major frame in 11 instances (across social movement documents and parliamentary debates) and minor frame in four.

² Present in five country cases; major frame in four instances and minor frame in five.

³ Present in five country cases; major frame in five instances and minor frame in three.

⁴ Present in five country cases; major frame in three instances and minor frame in six.

⁵ Present in five country cases; major frame in three instances and minor frame in five.

WP2: GBV																
Frame	Denmark		France		Greece		Italy		Poland		Slovenia		Spain		Turkey	
	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD	SM	PD
Gender-based Violence: Redefining violence	Major	Minor														
Gender-based Violence: Violence as universal	Minor		Major	Minor	Minor	Minor			Major	Minor			Minor			
Gender-based Violence: Structural violence	Minor	Minor	Major	Minor	Major	Minor	Major	Minor	Major	Minor	Minor		Major	Minor	Major	Minor
Health and Reproductive Rights: Bodily autonomy	Major	Minor					Minor	Minor	Minor	Minor	Major	Minor			Minor	
Health and Reproductive Rights: Healthy life				Minor			Minor		Minor	Minor						
Intersectional Frames: Class consciousness			Major		Minor	Minor	Major	Minor			Major	Minor			Minor	Minor
Intersectional Frames: LGBTQ+ rights			Minor	Minor	Minor		Minor								Major	Minor
Intersectional Frames: Racism and nationalism			Major		Major		Minor	Minor							Major	
Political-economic Frames: Contested gender equality			Major	Minor			Major	Minor	Minor		Minor				Major	Minor
Political-economic Frames: Critique of politics as usual			Minor				Minor	Minor							Major	Minor
Political-economic Frames: Human rights and fundamental freedom	Minor						Minor	Minor			Major	Minor			Major	Minor
Political-economic Frames: Value of women's work							Major	Minor							Minor	

Table 2 Overview of GBV frames per country and document type

Social movement documents (SM) marked with purple and parliamentary debates (PD) marked with yellow; dark coloring denotes major frames and light coloring, minor frames.

As mentioned, one frame stands out as the most significant one across the analysis of the eight GBV campaigns. The predefined GBV frame, 'Structural violence', as set out in the coding guidelines, emphasizes that GBV is understood as a structural problem and highlights that it is essential to critically analyze and oppose the unequal power structures which are sustained by and are expressed through violence. Critical concepts emphasizing the structural nature of the problem, such as 'rape culture', are often used in relation to this frame. In this frame, structural violence is typically associated with patriarchal exercise of power, rise of traditionalism, and/or reactions to loss of (men's) privileges. It can also address systemic and institutional violence (e.g., carried out by the state or the church) and how violence is used to control and dominate women in the public and the private sphere. The prognosis of this frame might include considerations regarding the material consequences of violence as well as the need for economic empowerment and gender education.

All of the predefined frames were identified in one or several of the country cases in the analysis of the GBV campaigns. In some country cases, other frames were identified (bottom-up) as well in relation to the theme. This concerns, for instance, Health and Reproduction Rights Frames in the case of Slovenia ('Anti-discrimination'; 'Universal healthcare'); Indigeneity/inalienability of legislation as a major frame in the case of Turkey; and an Intersectional Frame related to 'Climate justice' and a Political-economic Frame on 'Quality of democracy' in the case of Italy. However, most of these additional frames were weighted as minor in the articulation in each country case.

As for the other selected campaign in each national case (i.e., not GBV), there was, again, slightly more diversity of frames across the social movement documents as compared to parliamentary debates. The main frame across the other themes was quite clearly the Political-economic Frame, 'Human rights and fundamental freedoms'. This was a major frame in nine cases (across social movement documents and parliamentary debates). Other crosscutting frames were 'Bodily autonomy' and 'Structural violence' as well as the Intersectional Frames, 'LGBTQ+ rights' and 'Racism and nationalism', although to a much lesser extent (each one was a major frame in only three cases). LGBTQI+ was covered as a theme in several of the countries (France, Greece, Slovenia). Intersectional Frames were very important in relation to this theme, especially in the French case as well as in the Greek analysis; however, Intersectional Frames were not present in relation to the theme in Slovenia. Further differences can be found across the three cases as GBV frames were important in the Greek case; GBV and Health and Reproductive Rights Frames in the French case; and none of these in the Slovenian case. Political-economic Frames were common in relation to LGBTQI+ campaigns across the three cases but to varying extent: in Slovenia these were the only frames and very important whereas they were only minor in Greece and present as both major/minor frames in the case of the French documents. The labour market theme was covered in the analyses of Spain and Denmark; subthemes differed as the Spanish case addressed domestic care work and the Danish one, equal pay. However, in both cases the Political-economic frame, 'Value of women's work', was the main frame (for both types of documents in the Spanish case and only social movement documents in the Danish case) whereas the Intersectional frame, 'Class Consciousness', was a major frame in social movement documents in Spain as well as a minor frame in parliamentary debates in Spain and social movement documents in Denmark. In-depth analyses will be carried out in relation to single country cases, comparative studies of a selection of the cases, as well as transversal dimensions of the analyses (e.g., focusing on specific codes, such as emotions, across all cases and campaigns) in the next steps of the project.

In the following we will take a closer look at the most important patterns that we find in the critical frame analysis across country cases, campaign themes, and document types. Contrary to the findings of the CFA of anti-gender/anti-feminist documents in WP1 (with coherence and strength of the common

framing), what stands out, first of all, in the CFA across country cases and themes in WP2 are the *variations in frames and significant differences* across cases and themes. However, the awareness of structural violence (as the major frame across all cases) is a common feature and the acknowledgement of the seriousness of the issue of GBV and the significant attention paid to this by feminists. In a broader perspective we find the *articulation of a complex analysis* and understanding of current problems to be present in most cases. This goes beyond the critique of existing policies and models and general calls for social change in a feminist direction: the underlying framing of gender inequality problems, that the actors set forward, rests on an analysis of intersecting systems of oppression and the intertwined dimensions of capitalism, racism, homo/transphobia, nationalism, colonialism, classism, and sexism that are the root causes of the problems that the feminist actors identify and frame (Spain, France, Greece, Italy). Similarly, the prognostic dimensions combine radical, intersectional feminism with anticapitalism/anti-neoliberalism. The different forms of oppression are considered to be gendered and intersecting and they permeate all themes and areas, from the value of women's work to the class dimension of violence, as articulated in the Italian case. This also results in a broadening of the feminist movements and their scope and demands. In the Greek case, in particular, environmental destruction, with a gendered dimension, is added to the intertwined forms of oppression. However, the aspiration for radical change or not also becomes a differential factor when we compare across country cases, with Denmark as the most visible outlier with a lack of explicit anticapitalism and intersectional feminist critique, for instance.

In many of the coded documents, we find a tendency to *focus more on the diagnosis* rather than the prognosis. Whereas elaborate understandings of the ways in which specific policy problems are tied to structural and systemic dimensions and institutions (such as cultural norms, education, media, role of religion, and state institutions) abound, the prognosis is often articulated as diffuse and general, whether as change in culture and public opinion (Denmark; France), e.g., related to consent, or as education (Spain). In the Polish case, for instance, demands related to specific policy measures (e.g., medical care, support measures for rape victims) were however combined with focus on more general social change, but with a clear emphasis on the former. Most often the state is considered to be the active actor, i.e., the one causing the problem, whether by controlling women's bodies and reproduction (Poland) or by hierarchizing citizenship and prioritizing wealthy and white citizens in its policies (France), for instance. The inability of the state to solve the intersecting problems in a systemic and structural manner, or its lack of willingness to do so, is a key element cutting across the diagnostic framing and pattern.

As regards document types, we find differences but also overlaps between *social movement documents and parliamentary debates*. Whereas social movement documents to a higher extent articulated intersectional frames and problem understandings, parliamentary debates tended to be less radical and confrontational in the feminist framings. In the Spanish case for instance parliamentary interventions did not articulate an anti-capitalist critique and instead strategically included social citizenship as a norm. In the Polish case there were no strong differences between the two types of documents but rather an interconnection between the frames that were articulated across the documents, all with a main focus on policy change. This created the groundwork for interconnectedness and coherence of frames. On the contrary, in the Greek case, we see parliamentary debates focusing on legal solutions whereas social movement documents are multidimensional by advocating for structural and legislative changes as well as awareness-raising and influence on public opinion, i.e., social change. The Italian case is also interesting as both types of documents frame the contested issue of education as well as violence as matters of 'quality of democracy, citizenship formation and social cohesion', thereby strategically shifting the focus and framing of an otherwise anti-institutional feminist movements towards

interaction with institutions and policy change. Like in the French case, in/exclusion from citizenship, in broad perspective, becomes a key component of the strategic framing and demands.

In many ways the contextual analysis of the campaigns shows that *change has been driven by social movements* in general and the feminist movements in particular, whether in terms of agenda-setting (e.g., of domestic care work in the Spanish case, or ecofeminism in Spain and Greece) or understandings of key issues, such as education, as structural and intersectional, like in Italy. The feminist movements call for radical change and paradigm shifts but, in some cases, we also see how feminist mobilization is reactive, when responding to anti-gender tendencies, like in the Slovenian case. Either way the *importance of alliances and the strategy of coalition-building* is emphasized across the cases, most clearly in relation to feminist and LGBTQI+ activists (France, Slovenia, Turkey). This is inherent to the *shift towards radical intersectional feminism* which we see as a crosscutting dimension. Feminist revolt (as opposed to state feminism) (Turkey) and development of feminist emancipatory potential (as a result of the reactive strategy) (Slovenia) are underlined and tie logically to the intersectional development of feminist mobilization, requiring transformative and radical change. Some tensions (e.g., between TERFs and intersectional feminists in the Spanish case) are brewing within the movement as well but these do not stand out significantly in the coded material. Feminist movements also take different approaches to mentioning anti-gender/antifeminist actors explicitly as opponents: in some cases, anti-gender concerns are absent from the documents (Denmark) or references are made to 'oppressive structures', e.g., instead (Spain) while others directly attack these actors in their framing (Poland, Slovenia) or call out the government and its role in creating a 'hostile mobilization environment', produced by state repression and erosion of democracy, like in the Turkish case.

Regarding the overall interpretation codes, there is quite a lot of *diversity in the ways in which gender and gender equality are understood*. Gender is articulated as binary in some contexts (Denmark, Italy/parliamentary debates, Slovenia) and non-binary in others (Greece, Turkey) or articulated broadly as a social construction (Italy, Turkey). A *significant presence of intersecting inequalities* is characteristic of most of the cases, especially in social movement documents; apart from gender, inequalities include class, age, nationality, race, and sexuality. A major silence in this regard is people with functional diversity, as pointed out in the Spanish analysis. Intersectionality is not always clearly defined (Denmark); in some cases, it is articulated as additive (Italy) and/or mutually constitutive (Greece, Italy, Slovenia). The understanding of gender equality also differs, ranging from non-articulation (Denmark) or anti/non-discrimination (Greece, Turkey) to feminist (collective) empowerment (Italy, Poland, Turkey) and transformation of power structures (Italy, Turkey). In some contexts, feminist social movement actors refrain from using gender equality as a term because it is considered reformist and not radical; instead, it is substituted by terms such as 'value of care' or 'sustainability of life' instead (Spain). Finally, there is a *lack of minority voices* present in the texts at times (Denmark); others criticize the invisibility of minorities (in data and discourse) (Greece) or recognize the influence of afrofeminist and antiracist groups on feminist mobilization today (France) with several of the movements, across country cases, identifying as intersectional feminists.

Emotions are also used and expressed in different ways across the coded documents. Three patterns emerge: 1) social movements use *rational, factual language* to avoid common gendered stereotypes (related to caring and emotions as female characteristics) and a depiction of women as victims, often times with legal references (Spain, Italy, Slovenia); 2) *gratitude* for what has been achieved by feminist actors in the past and *hope* for what they can achieve in the future as well as *empathy* for target groups (Denmark, Spain, France, Slovenia, Turkey); and 3) *anger and frustration* expressed as reactions to anti-gender tendencies and actors along with *anxiety* as regards institutional politics and failed solutions

(Denmark, France, Poland, Slovenia, Turkey). The emotional weight is particularly present in social movement documents, and it serves as a part of the mobilization strategy both in terms of gaining support for and/or consensus behind specific policy proposals and to mobilize public opinion. The Greek case stands out: instead of counteracting the image of women as more emotional by using rational language as part of the mobilizing strategy, movements use anger in combination with expressions of love, care and vulnerability as a way to oppose masculine politics. This is expressed, for instance, in relation to silent mourning for GBV victims in public spaces as a way to defy politics as usual and make 'politicized affectivity' an integral part of their activism.

4.2. Conclusions

The importance of the findings stemming from the CFA data stream relate to the way in which the in-depth analysis of frames and patterns sheds light on similarities, variations, and differences across the country cases as well as the way in which they can contribute to answering key questions of WP3 that cut across cases and themes. The latter includes questions such as which frames are used by feminist actors to influence public opinion and policy development, what determines (legal) change (or the lack thereof), how and when feminist mobilization becomes an enabling factor of change (socially and politically), and how framings (through strategies) influence both policy and public opinion. This includes analyzing the role of feminist movements, their framings, strategies, and mobilization dynamics not just in relation to institutional politics but also beyond. By connecting the CFA findings with the other data streams (interviews, DNA), we can address these questions and contextualize them in relation to policy processes, actors and dynamics of mobilization, influence and power in campaigns.

The CFA summary across all cases and themes point out important analytical ideas and arguments to be pursued further in the next phases of the project. A key question to be explored is to what extent we are witnessing a *shift in the content and strategy of feminist mobilization* and demands where the current state of feminist mobilization can be considered a conjuncture of change characterized by complexity and some dispersion but potentially on the way to forming cohesion, at least in some areas. The intersecting systems of oppression which are articulated as part of the diagnosis suggest a thread of a cohesive discourse but one which is still broad and abstract and, in many cases, has not found its translation into specific, comprehensive prognoses. The *complex structural analysis of intersecting inequalities* and how they permeate system and society marks a shift in the debate, in terms of frames, alliances, and repertoires (like feminist strikes as comprehensive strategy of mobilization cutting across themes and groups). Feminist mobilization has opened a broader field of themes and engagement for gendered and intersectional analysis in recent years where antagonism is also defined broadly, i.e., in terms of economic and political models as well as social norms and values. As suggested in the Italian case, this could mark a materialist turn, with recurrent references to a variety of social inequalities as well as economic models, citizenship, and democracy, as well as structural concerns in general. As noted in the Turkish analysis, there is a need, however, for further exploring what exactly is meant by 'structure' across different contexts. Whereas the antagonist anti-gender discourse is often considered cohesive across themes (see WP1 CFA summary report), in the case of the feminist actors there seems to be consensus regarding the shift but also significant differences which might suggest an *emerging cohesion*, potentially provoked by the need for reaction against anti-gender tendencies. The GBV theme is influential in this sense and the critical frame analysis shows how there is a shift in framing towards a common articulation of the issue as structural violence, including cultural, political, and economic dimensions. This framing is both a cause of change and an outcome of feminist mobilization in numerous contexts.

A related question concerns the *role of alliances* in the shift and the potential road towards cohesion. So far, the analyses show that alliances serve different functions, whether as a solution to ensure efficient policies; an expression of intersectionality in practice; or the necessary common ground to ensure collaboration across political divides. In relation to the future of feminism, it is likewise interesting to consider how and when *empowerment and feminist solidarity can overcome exclusions*, both in terms of policy influence (need for radical change) as well as internally in the movements. In a broader perspective this also relates to inclusiveness in terms of democracy and how intersectionality plays a role in this (including the potential of inclusive framing in relation to religion and faith, as discussed in relation to the Turkish feminist movement).

Democracy, citizenship, and state-citizen relations cut across the coded material as important elements of analysis. In the framings, the common enemy of the feminist movement are anti-gender actors and/or the government or state. Whereas some actors deliberately choose not to mention anti-gender actors explicitly or engage with them in any way, others attack them directly and turn the opposition into a dimension of their framing of the problems (anti-gender actors as active actors causing the problem, e.g.). *State as enemy* is articulated in the critique of lack of democratic quality and failure to achieve equality, protect all citizens, and ensure proper implementation of legislative changes when adopted. Emotional language and framing are used to express and mobilize this critique of the government and the state. Emotions include anger, frustration, and outrage regarding inequality and injustices in relation to the differential treatment of citizens (also in an intersectional perspective) where governments and state institutions are seen as complicit in eroding gender equality, fostering backlash, and leading towards de-democratization.

Another crucial dimension of analysis is *strategic framing and (de)gendering* where actors, for instance, seek to maximize their possibility of influence by adapting their framings, and the use of gendered or degendered terms, to the political context. This is apparent in several ways in the CFA findings, whether in the non-gendered articulations of the frame 'Bodily autonomy' to ensure an inclusive approach to reproductive rights for all, or the strategic linguistic shifts used to gain voice in institutional settings, often implying a deradicalized and liberal framing of problems (depending on the theme at hand) – or in related terms, as in the Turkish case, the need to articulate the narrative of the feminist movement and its indigeneity to counteract opposite framings articulated by anti-gender actors (feminism as a foreign imposition).

Whereas our analysis in the subsequent phases of the project will focus mainly on crosscutting dimensions, it remains interesting to further study the differences between country cases, or clusters of cases, as well. Here, the findings of CFA call for attending to the issue of what determines the *target and objective of demands* to understand differences between (exclusive) focus on legal and political change (mainly in parliamentary debates) and/or cultural and normative change as an aim. Our findings show that the frames articulated by the feminist movements oftentimes place *more emphasis on diagnosis than prognosis*; this can be the result of non-institutional aims of mobilization and/or the difficult translation of the complexity of the diagnosis into specific policy aims and outcomes; causes and consequences of this dynamic need to be further explored. There is more focus on policy change when movements are reactive, for instance.

Similarly, a division cuts across the material as regards *reformist versus radical strategies of mobilization*; here, it is particularly interesting to see how and why some movements and contexts seem to be less prone to or apt in terms of fully taking on intersectional practices and demands although they may share for instance a structural framing of GBV. Intersectionality is used differently in the different campaigns, and the challenge in *introducing intersectional perspectives into institutional politics* remains; this

results in oversimplification and silencing of intersectional systems of oppression. The process of introducing intersectionality into institutions, and the risk of watering down the complex, intersectional analysis, need to be analyzed further in relation to policy influence.

Finally, the *mobilizing use of emotions* warrants further analysis. Several interesting aspects have become evident from the cross-cutting analysis. This includes the way in which the use of emotions points in several directions: rationality as a strategic device to counteract gendered stereotypes and expectations in political debate and oppose anti-gender discourses; emotions as driving force for activism and the development of politicized affectivity; as well as the role and function of emotions in creating solidarity and inclusive communities based on care, as underlined by the Greek analysis. In addition, the focus on emotions has also shown how *silence becomes a tool of activism and power*, both when deciding to use the silence strategically and when deciding to break the silence for minorities to gain voice, for instance.

References

- Dombos, Tamas with Krizsan, Andrea, Verloo, Mieke & Zentai, Violetta (2012): *Critical Frame Analysis: A Comparative Methodology for the 'Quality in Gender+ Equality Policies' (Quing) project*, Center for Policy Studies, Working Paper Series. Budapest: CEU.
- Ferree, Myra M., William A. Gamson, Jürgen Gerhards & Dieter Rucht (2002): *Shaping Abortion Discourse: democracy and the public sphere in Germany and the United States*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press.
- Verloo, Mieke (2005): "Mainstreaming gender equality in Europe. A critical frame analysis." *The Greek Review of Social Research*, 117(B), 11–35.

Appendix A: FIERCE codebook

Title of the document	
1	Coding entry number (Country+Type of actor+Type of document+Number of coding+title of the document in English) (Type of actor: feminist/FEM, anti-gender/AG) (Type of document: Parliamentary debate/POL, social movement/SOCMOV)

1. Document variables	
1	Full title of document (English) (automatically generated)
2	Date of coding (DD.MM.YYYY) (automatically generated)
3	Name of coder (automatically generated)
4	Date of text (DD.MM.YYYY)
5	Type of document (feminist, anti-gender)
6	Author of text (individual, including position, i.e., named MP/spokesperson of a party, in the case of interventions from parliamentary debates, or organization/movement)
7	Type of text (parliamentary debate, social movement)
8	Central theme (labour market, health and reproductive rights, migration, LGBTQ+ rights, GBV, other)

2. Diagnosis	
1	How is the problem defined? This might require synthesizing longer descriptions or definitions of the problem into shorter statements.
2	Why is it considered a problem? What are considered the causes of the problem?
3	Is the problem primarily considered structural or individual?
4	Who is considered responsible for causing the problem? (active actor)
5	Who is considered to be affected by the problem? (passive actor)
6	What are the main norms that the author of the text is expressing in the diagnosis?
7	What are the main underlying norms that are used to support the framing of the problem?

3. Prognosis	
1	What is proposed (if anything) as a solution to the problem?
2	Is the proposed solution primarily considered structural or individual?
3	What is the vision or the objective of the proposed solution?
4	Which strategy (if any) is advocated to solve the problem? Which actions (if any) are envisaged to achieve the goal?
5	Does the proposed solution include any specific (policy) action or instrument? [fixed options: legal change; new institution/policy; abolish institution/policy; in/decrease budget; improve implementation; public awareness campaign; information/statistics; coalition-building; other]
6	Who is responsible for solving the problem and implementing the solution? (active actor)
7	Who is the beneficiary or target group of the proposed solution? (passive actor)
8	What are the main norms that the author of the text is expressing in the prognosis?
9	What are the main underlying norms that are used to support the framing of the solution?

4. Overall interpretation	
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1	[If relevant] Which understanding(s) of gender [biological; binary; non-binary; social practice; deconstructed; intersectional; degendered] are present in the text?
2	[If relevant] Which understanding(s) of gender equality [means to policy goal; end in itself; equality as sameness/equal treatment; equality as difference/positive action; equality as transformation; non/anti-discrimination] are present in the text?
3	Which inequality categories, if any, are mentioned in the articulation of the problem and its solution? [fixed options: gender; ethnicity; religion; class; sexual orientation; age; disability; marital/family status; nationality/migrant status; other/specify]
4	[If relevant] Are the inequality categories mentioned in the text considered to be intersecting?
5	Are minority voices explicitly addressed in the text? Please explain in which way the issue is addressed, i.e., in inclusionary or exclusionary ways [if relevant]
6	What is the main emotion (if any) that is expressed through the description or articulation of the problem and the solution in the text? [fixed options: empathy/compassion/affection; trust; fear/anxiety; distrust/uncertainty; anger/frustration; envy; shame; disgust; hope, other/specify]

5. Frames

1	What are the immediate (diagnostic and prognostic) frames that you would identify in the text based on the coding? [list of predefined frames; open category]
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Document memo

1	<p>Please provide a short description of the policy context, including any references (mentioned in the text) to previous success or failure in agenda-setting, change of frames, policy input, policy adoption, and/or policy change. Make reference (if relevant) to previous parliamentary debates or campaigns on the same issue within the 2010-2022 period as well as the result of the policy process (i.e., adoption/rejection of new policies; relevant policy influence achieved).</p> <p>In addition, please provide a short description of references (mentioned in the text) to previous success or failure in coalition-building, alliance-building, networking, co-organized demonstrations, and/or collective campaigning for policy change, internal conflicts, split-ups, e.g. Include in the description any references to civil society/state interaction, processes of participation, deliberation, and/or specific forms of decision-making processes (whether as inclusion or exclusion).</p>
2	Are there any significant silences in the text that you would be able to identify based on your reading of the text and knowledge of the field from the FIERCE literature reviews?

Appendix B: Full description of predefined frames

Based on the FIERCE literature reviews, carried out at country-level as well as for the EU, we identified a set of frames which were used as predefined categories in the codebook and in the coding software. Likewise, there was an open option which allowed for the coding of other (immediate) frames, not covered by the list but identified through the analysis and coding of the text in question; these immediate frames were identified by considering the problem statement, the active/passive actors, and the underlying norms. All frames (the predefined ones as well as the ones emerging from the analysis of the specific text) were important for the analysis of frames across countries and themes.

The predefined *feminist frames* (WP2) are described in the following.

Intersectional frames

Intersectional frames posit a connection between different inequalities as well as between the struggles and social conditions of women and other groups. These frames focus on intersecting forms of oppression as well as intersecting perspectives on opportunities for solidarity and collaboration. Intersectional frames distinguish between various identity markers that partly separate individuals and groups from each other while, at the same time, focusing on shared concerns and unity of action. The most recurrent *Intersectional frames* are “LGBTQ+ rights”, “Class consciousness”, and “Racism and nationalism”.

LGBTQ+ rights	The frame is related to collaborations between the feminist and LGBTQ+ movements on issues such as gender-based violence and health & reproductive rights. Diagnostically, it emphasizes that patriarchal traditions and structures, such as heteronormativity, affect both women and LGBTQ+ groups. This is sometimes related to ideas on deconstruction of “gender” and “gender identity”.
Class consciousness	The frame highlights that economic conditions influence gender (in)equality in significant ways. This means that feminist struggles should not ignore the ways in which class differences intersect with gender in the types of oppression that feminist movements are mobilizing against. In some contexts, class consciousness is coupled with a clear anti-capitalist critique, which also connects feminism to left-wing politics, and sometimes this frame comes to the fore in relation to discussion on austerity politics and its consequences.
Racism and nationalism	The frame considers racism and sexism to be significant intersecting forms of oppression. In diagnostic terms, the modern nation-state and nationalism are oppressive mechanisms of ‘othering’ and exclusion that have been normalized and function in similar ways to patriarchal structures. Migrant women and LGBTQ+ refugees are often perceived as the most vulnerable groups.

Gender-based violence frames

Gender-based violence frames put a critical focus on the type of violence that is connected to gender and often also sexuality. This is often framed in terms of causality, emphasizing the structural reasons of violence as a problem of unequal gender power structures and gendered oppression as well as the genderedness of the perpetrator/victim relation (men as perpetrator and women as victims). At times this is furthered discussed in relation to issues such as toxic masculinity norms, for instance. The most prominent *Gender-based violence frames* are “Structural violence” and “Violence of patriarchy”.

Structural violence	The frame emphasizes that gender-based violence is a structural problem: It highlights that it is essential to critically analyze and oppose the unequal power structures which are sustained by and are expressed through violence. Critical concepts emphasizing the structural nature of the problem, such as ‘rape culture’, are often used in relation to this frame. Most often, structural violence is associated, in this frame, with the patriarchal exercise of power, rise of traditionalism, and/or reactions to loss of (men’s) privileges. It can also address systemic and institutional violence (e.g., carried out by the state or the church) and how violence is used to control and dominate women in the public and the private sphere. The prognosis of this frame might include considerations regarding the material consequences of violence as well as the need for economic empowerment and gender education.
Violence as universal	The frame underlines that gender-based violence is a broad concept and a problem which can affect all women. It emphasizes the need for mutual support and solidarity between women since they are all victims of violence and, thus, aims to mobilize women with diverse religious, national, and ethnic backgrounds. At times the frame is related to the idea of ‘women’s rights as human rights’.

Political-economic frames

Political-economic frames emphasize the importance of the most fundamental structures of society whether these are, e.g., constitutional rights, social reproduction, or economic security. These frames are broad in their scope given that they focus on issues that relate to the population as a whole. Human rights violations are often not raised only on behalf of women or LGBTQ+ persons but claimed to affect everyone regardless of gender or sexuality. Among the *Political-economic frames* are “Contested gender equality”, “Care work”, “Human rights and fundamental freedoms”, as well as “Critique of ‘politics as usual’”.

Contested gender equality	The frame criticizes mainstream and/or anti-gender discourses and considers them to be part of the problem of the lack of progress or even backlash in terms of rights and gender equality. Thus, this frame is a reaction to growing anti-gender/anti-feminist politics as well as the argument that gender equality has been achieved or has gone too far. Related to the frame is a strong critique of homophobia, nationalism, racism, and/or misogyny.
Value of women’s work	The diagnosis of this frame typically relates to the ways in which care work is not perceived as being as valuable as other types of work and, thus, underpaid in the labor market. In general, the frame emphasizes that women’s role in society is not valued enough. Care work is feminized and carried out by women in the public as well as in the private sphere. The frame often highlights the connections between paid and unpaid care work as undervalued activities, as well as the issue of precarity and domestic workers’ rights.
Human rights and fundamental freedoms	This frame underlines the lack of human rights and fundamental freedoms as the main problem and, consequently, focuses on the protection of these

	as the prognosis. Particularly for contentious issues, such as abortion, fundamental freedoms and human rights are repeatedly referred to as a minimal form of protection for everyone in society which should therefore also include women and LGBTQ+ persons. Human rights are often perceived as a universal political language that makes it easier to engage in dialogue with political adversaries in the public sphere or call for international condemnation in cases where there is a more polarized environment.
Critique of ‘politics as usual’	The diagnosis of this frame rests on the contemporary state of democracy and the current (lack of) possibilities for creating change. It includes a critique of conventional, institutionalized politics. Proponents of this frame posit a clear difference between their own civil society activities and the work done by parties, politicians, and public servants. In the diagnosis, the active actor includes religious and political actors, depending on the context. At times the prognosis is related to conceptualizing pluralist forms of democracy (acknowledging differences) and democratic innovations within the movements (e.g., experiments with new forms of decision-making).

Health and reproduction frames

Health and reproduction frames are characterized by a focus on personal life, bodily autonomy, as well as mental and physical health. These frames usually revolve around a defense of women’s bodily autonomy but they also include other demands, such as better healthcare for LGBTQ+ persons and calls to reconsider what mental health and quality of life mean with an emphasis on mutual interdependence and care as a relational practice. In this regard, the feminist struggle is perceived as something that the population as a whole can relate to and benefit from (similar to the political-economic frames). The *Health and reproduction frames* are “Bodily autonomy” and “Healthy life”.

Bodily autonomy	This frame is mainly related to women’s right to bodily autonomy and the struggle for right to free abortion, but it is also articulated in relation to other issues, such as beauty ideals and body positivity, transgender rights, and sexual harassment. In its prognosis, the frame addresses the inherent connection between bodily autonomy and fundamental freedoms, and aims to liberate women’s bodies from excessive attention, control, and violations.
Healthy life	The diagnosis of this frame emphasizes the propagation of erroneous ideas about what a good and healthy life means. This is caused by patriarchal ideology, including, for instance, excessive beauty ideals, a scientific and machinist approach to the body, as well as prioritization of career and prestige over family and personal relations. These ideas are harmful not only to women and LGBTQ+ persons but to society as a whole.

5. Introduction to the research stream: DNA

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In this introduction, we first explain the Discourse Network Analysis (DNA), delineating the steps of data collection and analysis, including the types of maps produced. We then discuss the advantages and potential limitations of the methodology and end with a summary of the key findings. This introduction is followed by a section on key findings that provides a comprehensive overview based on aggregated data from national cases and country reports.

5.1. Methodological steps

Discourse Network Analysis (DNA) is a specific type of social network analysis (SNA), which identifies advocacy coalitions based on the policy preferences of actors. DNA transforms text data (e.g., newspaper articles) into a list of statements. First, a predetermined list of keywords signifying contextually specific events, campaigns, and debates are brought together. These keywords are then used to pull data (articles, news items, op-eds, reports) from a comparable range of newspapers in each country case for a specified period. DNA coding captures a policy issue, the actor who speaks about this policy (names, organizations), and whether they are speaking favorably or unfavorably about it on a particular date/event. DNA coding involves coding the date of the statement, name of the actor / organization, policy issue, and the actor's position towards the issue (positive or negative) in a software, called Discourse Network Analyzer. After the data is cleaned and transformed into a tidy format, bar charts and network maps are produced. The steps of the analysis are explained below:

Newspaper selection

In designing our newspaper selection, the consortium relied on the already developed indicator of high-quality press, a criterion defined in terms of wide circulation, reputation and moderate political positioning (Barranco & Wisler, 1999). So, the newspaper sales figures matter to the extent that country specific knowledge indicates that this reflects the expanse of coverage. The objective was detecting as many actors and policy issue areas as possible while not inundating the coders with too much repeat information on any single event. In other words, a balance was to be struck between diversity of coverage and limiting the corpus so that repeat information could be minimized.

Across the consortium, in cases where there are reputable newspapers, the minimal and sufficient number of newspapers included in the search was 2 newspapers: one with a moderate-left and the other with a moderate-right position. This selection was based on the goal of obtaining the broadest possible coverage of both right wing and left wing voices, with the expectation that a moderate-left wing newspaper would cover a broad spectrum of voices but would be more likely to cover left wing voices more and a moderate right-wing positioned newspaper would also cover a broad spectrum of voices, but would be more likely to capture more of the right wing voices (Barranco & Wisler, 1999). However, in some countries because the political scene was more fractured to the extent that certain voices can only be captured if certain outlets are included, each team decided on the number of additional newspapers depending on political context. The limitations in the available databases also played a role in the selection of additional newspapers, where relevant. The newspaper selection criteria were specified in a document of written guidelines shared with everyone.

Other rules that the consortium set for comparability, shared also in the guidelines, included the following: When the same event, same actors, and their public speeches are reported across different newspapers, duplicate coding is avoided. Opinion pieces will be excluded from the material to be coded since the goal is to capture news about actors speaking (Leifeld 2013). Four or five consecutive years were chosen for the gathering of the data from the newspapers selected, depending on context. The rule is that these years would have to be consecutive and would not start at a year earlier than 2015. If there was a specific and hot debate which would increase data points for any year, this rule gave the teams some flexibility while retaining coherence.

Keyword selection

For purposes of striking a balance between the doability of the work, capturing the richness of each country case, and retaining comparability, the consortium made the decision that everyone uses the following keywords and their grammatical iterations in gathering the articles from the newspapers chosen: *Gender, LGBT, Feminist*. We held country-specific meetings and a consortium level meeting to review the keyword and newspaper selections leading up to the gathering of articles. Given the existence of linguistic and contextual differences (for example, cases where “gender” is not a common word or when the three words cannot capture an important and specific theme/event/debate), we decided that the project teams can replace the word gender with another linguistically appropriate keyword, such as gender equality. When gender was too broad, the project teams could add other keywords to capture country specific debates on important events, laws, international conventions, such as same-sex marriage, mandatory shared custody, Istanbul Convention, etc. The rules everyone followed in the selection of additional keywords were the following: The keywords should be as “neutral” as possible or should include the namings used prevalently by feminists as well as anti-feminist actors so that both sides of the debate can show up in the articles gathered. Keywords should not be mistaken for policy areas to be coded. Each keyword should embody multiple issue areas. When an article is irrelevant, it should not be coded. Guidelines for keyword selection were also produced and shared with consortium partners.

Downloading the articles

In downloading the articles, depending on the structure of online media archives in the countries, five project teams used paid services by professional media companies, and three used publicly available newspaper archives. The number of articles gathered showed variation depending on country sizes, the degree of prominence of gender-related scenes in the general political scene, the variations in the degree of intensity of debates, and the coverage of the platforms through which the articles were obtained.

Determining the codebook

The leading team (KU) prepared an initial codebook that addressed the main themes of the project and covered debates that emerged from the literature reviews each team had written (D1.1 and D2.1). Once the initial list of codes on policy debates and their definitions was prepared, several consortium meetings were held to develop the definitions for clarity and add new, overlooked codes. Once the coding began, the coding teams met biweekly to discuss puzzling cases of coding. In the first few meetings of this period, new codes were iteratively added also, as new issues emerged from public debates encountered. The final codebook has a total of 85 concepts covering issues under the themes of marriage and family, education, health and reproductive rights, labor market, gender-based violence, LGBTQI+ rights, public life, and governance structure. In addition to these concepts, countries also utilized some additional concepts for country-specific issues.

Coding

Before coding began, we held two general workshops, both conducted twice to ensure participation from all project teams. One of these workshops was more general and focused on the logic of social network analysis and within it discourse network analysis. The second workshop delved further into discourse network analysis and the pragmatics of step-by-step coding within the software Discourse Network Analyzer. Furthermore, written guidelines were produced and shared with the project teams, covering the content of the workshops. As indicated before, throughout the coding period, biweekly meetings were held to discuss and resolve technical issues with the software, make consortium-wide decisions on how to code news items with less clarity, and iteratively revise timelines in accordance with the teams' progress.

Once the coding was finished, all databases were transferred to KU for data analysis and network visualization. The first stage of the analysis was the detection of possible errors, omissions and/or duplicates, followed by data cleaning. We employed the programming language R for data preprocessing and analysis due to its advanced capabilities and extensive packages suited to our research needs. We then transformed the data into a tidy format for performing descriptive analyses. Through these analyses, we identified the most active actors and debates within the dataset. Moreover, we generated network maps and performed network analysis techniques using specialized R packages to obtain various network-related measures.

After this phase, multiple maps and charts were produced by the KU team for each national case.

5.2. Maps and charts produced

This phase of the analysis consisted of producing charts of top actors and concepts for each country case and developing two-mode and one-mode network maps. Several different types of charts and maps were developed. The country teams were asked to write their reports, using only the maps and charts that revealed relevant and decipherable information. For example, if the number of coded entries were too large, the teams used different thresholds to remove actors which spoke only a handful of times. Or if there was no interesting information to glean from changes across time, they did not have to use those charts in their reports. Or if the communities detected in the cohesive subgroups did not reveal clear qualitative logics, beyond the algorithms the software utilized, they were not explicitly discussed.

Below is a discussion of all the maps and charts produced. In addition, KU prepared the raw data in excel formats enabling future analyses and use in publications with or without social network analysis focus. The team reports are based on their selections from these.

Top actors and concepts

This data adds up the number of statements and organizations that spoke over the years and visualizes them in two charts. If there are hundreds of organizations and most of the concepts in our codebook were used in the national cases, these charts take up the top 20 most active organizations or top 20 most debated concepts. In the charts on top debated concepts, the degree of agreement / disagreement is revealed through different colors used. We can garner the degree of disagreement from the proportion between the two colors.

By looking at these charts, the project teams were able to decipher who / what type of actors spoke most, whether the results tracked with other analyses and previous scholarship, whether there were surprises, what the balance appeared to be between feminist versus anti-feminist/ anti-gender actors at the top, who and what the absences were, what the top debated issues were, and what the degree

of agreements and disagreements looked like. Furthermore, because year by year comparisons of the top twenty concepts were provided, the researchers could look into how the top 20 debates had changed over time.

Monthly statements overview

This graph plots the number of statements made over the course of the analysis period for each country. This visualization enables the researchers to track when more heated debates were taking place across the entire time period for which the analysis was conducted.

Two-mode network maps

Two-mode networks show the relationship between the organizations and the concepts.

In two-mode network maps, each organization is connected to the concepts using a net tie calculation: the net opinion of an organization is obtained by subtracting negative statements from positive statements on any concept. Those organizations with a positive value are linked to the statements with green, and those with a negative value are linked with red. We can get the following information from these maps: 1) which organizations agree on any of the debates on a concept, 2) which organizations are confronting one another in any of the debates, and 3) which debates attract the most intense participation. The first type of two-mode network presents existing data in its raw form.

A second type of two-mode network, called **two-mode network with degree centrality**, probes more into the question of how central any organization or concept is. Degree centrality is one of the key metrics in network analysis, measuring the number of connections a node (organizations or concepts) has to others within the network. It indicates how central a particular node is. Nodes with a higher degree centrality are considered more active because they have more direct connections to other nodes. Degree centrality for an organization is based on the number of concepts an organization speaks about. Degree centrality for a concept is based on the number of organizations which speak about it.

In our case, a high degree centrality means that the organization has voiced their position on a large number of concepts. For the concepts, a high degree centrality indicates that a large number of organizations are making a statement on that concept. In the map, the size of the nodes (organizations or concepts) is proportional to their degree centrality. In this way, it is easy to spot the most connected actors and concepts on which the greatest number of actors speak. The charts for each case identify the names of the top 3 organizations and concepts in the ledger. For the teams to analyze the rest of the list, three additional tools were provided: an excel table which provides the information linking the organizations and the concepts in the form of a matrix; horizontal bar charts that rank the 20 actors and concepts with the highest degree centrality, and an interactive map allowing researchers to detect where each of the concepts and organizations are placed in terms of their connections.

These maps and charts enable researchers to explore the terrain of feminist and anti-feminist / anti-gender actors and the trends for organizational structures. They can determine whether there is a concentration of umbrella organizations, which speak on numerous issues, or if there is a heavy presence of single-issue organizational structures, or if they are equally present. Maps can probe into the characteristics of critical organizations, what types of organizations appear to be more active, whether there is an under- or over-representation of certain regions. An analysis of concepts on which more actors speak also gives indications about the level of controversies and agreements.

One-mode network maps

One-mode networks are formed for organizations by translating relationships using the two-mode networks. This conversion creates connections between organizations based on their shared relationships to the concepts in the two-mode network. In this network, a tie between two organizations exists if the sign of their net tie to a concept is the same (i.e., both positive or both negative).

One-mode network maps enable researchers to concentrate on discursive subgroups that organizations are part of based on their common relationships to shared concepts. The members of a subgroup agree on their approach to a particular concept. These sub-groups do not automatically mean that there is a physical relationship between the organizations, but it merely indicates that they agree on certain issues. However, this information can bolster our findings of alliances (or lack thereof) with what we know from other data collection streams.

These network maps also provide pivotal metrics, namely density, connectedness, and fragmentation, for understanding the network's overall structure. **Density** reflects the proportion of actual connections to the maximum possible connections among nodes, indicating how closely knit the network is. A higher density suggests more interconnected nodes, suggesting a tightly knitted network. **Connectedness** refers to the extent to which nodes in the network are directly or indirectly linked to one another. This means the degree to which the network enables us to start from one organization and travel to all other organizations in the network following existing links (edges). **Fragmentation** equals (1- Connectedness), and it measures the reverse of connectedness. A fragmented network has separate components, less overall cohesion, and more isolated actors / small groups of actors.

We have produced different visualizations of the one-mode network, leaving the decision of which ones to utilize to the research teams. These can be broadly categorized as **non-normalized one-mode network maps and normalized one-mode network maps**. In non-normalized network maps, we do not establish threshold rules for excluding actors based on connection strength. The absence of a threshold ensures that all potential connections based on shared concepts are represented, allowing for a comprehensive view of the network's structure. However, oftentimes, especially if the political terrain is crowded, this visualization can be too crowded. Thus, we have also produced a series of normalized network maps. In these maps, we have deployed thresholds to remove certain actors based on whether they pass a minimum number of connections or not. This additional normalization layer enables the creation of a less dense network, thus refining our understanding of the network's structure and the strength of its connections.

Each country was provided with five different types of non-normalized networks and several different iterations of the same maps with respect to at least one threshold.

One-mode (plain) network maps visualize how the terrain of organizations looks, enabling researchers to assess the degree of density, connectedness, and fragmentation without removing any organizations. The researchers can explore the connections between organizations, where actors that they are interested in are located, or examine which organizations are included in clusters or isolated positions. The normalized version of the same map enables a closer look at the organizations which pass the threshold, enabling researchers to identify critical organizations in the core, and explore their characteristics in terms of types, regional coverage, situation with respect to relevant cleavages.

One-mode network maps with degree centrality reveal how central any organization is. The map is based on a calculation of centrality, based on which organizations share similar positions with others to a greater extent. Thus, an organization with high degree centrality shares more similar positions with organizations than others. Using this map together with the bar chart for the top 20 organizations with degree centrality the researchers are able to obtain information on the most connected actors and

analyze their characteristics, theorize the implications of their connections; explore the balance between feminist versus anti-feminist & anti-gender actors in terms of degree of connection and theorize the implications of this balance (or lack thereof) for the visibility of debates and processes of possible hegemonization on different issues.

One-mode network with betweenness centrality maps highlight those organizations that act as bridges between different clusters of organizations. High betweenness centrality indicates that an organization acts as a bridge between organizations that do not make statements on similar concepts. Used together with the relevant bar chart and qualitative data, this network map enables researchers to determine whether there are gatekeepers or bridges between separate clusters of organizations and explore what these mean for mobilization and network fragmentation possibilities.

One-mode network maps with degree and betweenness centrality combine the visual information in the separate maps explained in the above paragraphs.

The cohesive sub-groups maps detect groups of organizations, which are more densely connected to each other than the rest of the network. To do that, this map identifies and eliminates isolated nodes and uses different colors to indicate different subgroups. This is based on a calculation that applies the Louvain method for community detection within the network. The Louvain method optimizes modularity by quantifying the density of links inside communities compared to links between communities. In most cases, these subgroups need to be studied together with locally specific data to speak more in-depth about the actualization of these coalitions. If the subgroups are clear enough, the researchers can study the defining characteristics of the organizations within each community, exploring ideological positions, relationships with the state, political resources, etc.

As indicated previously, the multiplicity of maps produced enabled researchers in their reports to focus on those that make sense, have potential for comparison with results from other data streams and relevant literature. In the next section we explain the broad findings and potential for analysis that emerge from the national reports.

5.3. Contributions and limitations of DNA

The overall strength of DNA for studying feminist and anti-feminist mobilizations is its ability to capture the broader terrain in a manner qualitative data is unable to do so.

It is able to provide us with a **macro-level perspective**. First, it can determine **who speaks, who speaks most, and on what issues**. Such an analysis allows us to corroborate existing literature on the structure of the advocacy field and the relative degree of vocalization of different actors. We are also able to **categorize different types of actors**: this means we can explore what types of actors are more likely to have their voices heard on a national scale. While this analysis, for the most part, will reveal what existing research identifies, DNA is also able to **capture actors**, which might otherwise have gone unnoticed in more qualitative research. For example, in Slovenia, DNA reveals the significant role academic actors can play. Or it might reveal that actors thought to be more influential may not be speaking as much (Italy, Turkey).

The size of the networks can be used to investigate the degree to which the **gender debates are relevant / central** to the political terrain to the extent that they are captured by national newspapers.

DNA is also able to show the **structure of advocacy coalitions**, the strength of their **discursive connections**, and the extent to which **discursive polarizations** exist. For example, in Italy we see a **movement-counter-movement dynamic** whereby anti-feminists are more likely to react to feminist proclamations. In Turkey, we see that feminist demands far outnumber anti-feminist concerns and the

two do not always speak to one another except in specific debates. The ability to empirically show these allows us to study the political field in a holistic manner, identifying which groups of actors are likely to share ideational affinities and which groups of actors are likely to oppose one another, beyond those that identify explicitly as feminist or anti-feminist. In this manner, we are able to see that in the majority of the cases there is a distinct polarization in the debates. But we are also able to capture **discursive ambiguities of political actors**, those who adopt feminist positions in some areas and anti-feminist in others, and the implications of these from an analytical perspective.

DNA starts from a binary coding of discourses. While this means oversimplification is embedded in this methodology, the outputs generated from such coding reveals a quantified measure of **most debated policy areas**. This can be used to corroborate more qualitative research. The coding system also enables the capturing of the degree to which there is **agreement or disagreement** on specific debates. This opens up diverse theorization possibilities regarding the links between general and specific themes, the cooptation for regressive agendas versus advocacy for progressive agendas, areas that have achieved social consensus, and those marked by political conflict and struggle.

Analyzing discourses and debates across time has the potential to reveal what changes and what does not. This can be coupled with qualitative knowledge on policy shifts, government changes, significant political events specific to the polity. It can also provide possibilities for comparison across cases to reveal patterns such as we have done in the second section above.

The most obvious limitation of DNA is that it is based on a binary coding system, and it is a quantitative technique. This means that we capture actor positions in a binary fashion, and we are able to make part of the data only clean-cut pro- or anti- positions. However, actors can have political and discursive ambiguities. They can also have nuances in their approaches within specific policy debates. We were able to capture them to a certain extent in the contradictions between general agreements on broad concepts and their specific policy areas in which the actors were more polarized. Unearthing these more fully requires qualitative approaches, as in the interviews and critical frame analysis. In other words, DNA is limited by the limitations of quantitative approaches, which often require parsimony and, therefore, need to be used together with qualitative outputs for richer and thicker analysis. Such a combination could pinpoint discursive ambiguities. Yet another theorization possibility which emerges in some national cases is to highlight rhetorical statements about gender equality, women's rights and empowerment, etc. by comparing them with positions across more specific policy fields. Yet another way of overcoming the limitations of parsimony would be to combine DNA output with a close-up, qualitative analysis of statements such as is done with CFA.

DNA utilizes textual data, and this textual data is often bounded by newspaper coverage in the literature using this technique. In other words, less institutionalized and more informal actors, who might occupy more place in social media platforms than mainstream media, are less likely to be visible in this data. This is a limitation in that while actors with more resources and national reach are likely to be reported on, those which remain on the fringes will need other techniques for analysis. These fringe actors could be using other forms of power, including local grassroots organizing as well as behind-the-door lobbying. Capturing these requires more qualitative techniques or social media data analysis, when/if it is made available from Twitter.

The corpus is further limited by the exclusion of opinion pieces with the qualifier that the focus is on policy debates taking place between policy-related organizations. However, in some political contexts, op-ed columnists themselves may be important actors, which play a significant role in steering debates, garnering support for their side, etc. In cases where qualitative techniques reveal this to be the case,

DNA can be reorganized to capture the positions of such op-ed writers and/or results of DNA can be combined with critical frame analysis.

5.4. Summary of key findings

In all national contexts, **political parties play a key role** in the debates. While this finding partly comes from the choice of corpus, with newspaper data more likely to report on parties than other actors, it also speaks to the **centrality of gender related debates in mainstream politics**. We also see a predominant position for NGOs and coalitions of NGOs, with **more positions at the top going to the feminist organizations than anti-feminist and anti-gender** actors. Apart from Poland and Slovenia, and to some extent France, where we see anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations at the top, in the top twenty lists, right wing political parties advocate anti-feminist and anti-gender positions in all cases. Other organizations included in the top twenty lists of national reports include business associations (Denmark), professional associations (Spain, Turkey), labor unions (Denmark, Turkey, Italy), universities (Slovenia), other NGOs with a rights-based focus (Greece) and religious (Italy, Greece, and Slovenia). This contextually specific variation gives indications of nation-specific debates taking place during the period to which the data pulled belongs. More broadly it can lend itself to the proposal that gender debates are central to the political realm, beyond confrontations between feminist and anti-feminist actors.

General concepts such as women's rights and empowerment, gender equality, women's rights in the labor market appear to **generate broad consensus** among participants in these debates. Regardless of ideological positioning, most agree that women's rights, women's rights in the labor market, and gender equality should be promoted, and take a position against violence. However, there is a **contrast between this finding and the results in specific policy areas** through which these general objectives can be realized. Some national reports, thus, reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea, without the political intention to put it into practice (Italy, Greece, France, Slovenia, Turkey).

One set of debates that can be grouped together are issues pertaining to LGBTQ+ rights: these include the top positioning of **LGBTQ+ rights** as the concept on which the most number of statements were made in the aggregate data, as well as hate crime legislation, LGBTQ+ visibility in public spaces, gender ideology, legislation, promotion of (heterosexual) marriage and family, adoption rights, rights of children of same-sex couples and same sex marriage. Additional relevant debates were also included in the discrete top twenty lists: LGBTQ+ rights in the labor market (Poland), conversion therapy (Poland, Denmark); gender transitioning (Spain); gender recognition legislation for minors, access to surrogacy, bathroom access (Denmark), medically assisted reproductive rights (France and Slovenia). For this group of debates, the **degree of confrontation between feminist and anti-feminist / anti-gender positions appears strikingly large**, both for generalist concepts and specific policy issues. The parallel intensity of debates across the country cases offers another comparative analysis possibility.

Violence against women and domestic violence acts, Istanbul Convention, and resources of gender-based violence policy making and implementation also **figure prominently in most countries**. In addition, in single country lists we see other relevant themes such as rape or sexual consent, support services for survivors of GBV, penalties for sexual harassment (Denmark), spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse (Spain), child sexual abuse (France), consideration of extenuating circumstances, resources for GBV policy making and implementation, resources for protecting child

survivors of sexual abuse (Turkey, France). These findings point to the ongoing problems around gender-based violence in all cases.

The debate on cultural/community values, in conjunction with some articulations of the promotion of heterosexual families and freedom of attire, captures place-specific ideological stances. On the one hand, we have a debate between **right-wing anti-feminist and anti-gender actors who promote the ideas of cultural difference and “outside” imposition on national values** to reject demands for rights by feminist and LGBTQI+ activists (Turkey). On the other hand, we have **right wing groups who use racist stereotypes**, suggesting some communities are not respectful of rights and equality because of their faith or culture, to justify their anti-immigrant stances.

When the different two mode networks of the countries, reported in the national reports, are analyzed, in some countries, we see a more fragmented field and there is a diverse range of debates and organizations engaging in them (Denmark, Poland, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). In this group of cases the agreements and the disagreements on concepts crisscross and there is not a clear picture of polarization emerging. For others, we see more coherent and confronting advocacy communities revealing a greater degree of polarization (Italy, Turkey, France).

Nevertheless, the one-mode network maps reveal that when organizations take on a feminist position in a policy debate, they are likely to take a feminist position on other debates, as well. While other organizations such as labor unions, rights-based organizations and some other progressive actors are likely to align with feminist positions; religious leaderships, in cases where they are vocal, are more likely to align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions

In the **one mode network maps in the national reports, the anti-gender actors and the extreme right-wing actors lose their significance**. This may suggest several things. It could be that while they are vocal on a few issues, their positions do not have high purchase among the larger civil society terrain. Or they may be speaking on issues that do not attract other participants. Or it could be that some of these actors are more strategically involved in behind-the-door lobbying instead of attempting to gain public legitimacy. In many countries, in one mode maps with thresholds, the political polarization becomes readily visual, depicting a movement-counter-movement dynamic (Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Turkey). Sometimes, we can explain this polarization in more general terms of left versus right, and in some cases, clearer feminist and anti-feminist alliances can be named. In this latter group, it is often the case that the actors voicing feminist positions in debates form larger alliances (Slovenia, Turkey).

5.5. Key findings

In this section, we describe the patterns that emerge from the data more extensively. First, for summary purposes and for capturing the broad picture, we first aggregate the coded material from the national cases. We use this aggregate data to produce raw and normalized charts of top-twenty actors and debates across all the national cases. These charts are based on the assumption the coding stages took place in a comparable manner across the cases. In other words, we acknowledge that due to the differences in data sizes, the visualization in its raw form, has the danger of flattening out country-specific conditions and, in its normalized form, can create overdue emphasis for debates with less frequency emerging from contexts with less data points. Nevertheless, analyzed together with the data emerging from single case analyses, these aggregated charts can still point to patterns to be further investigated. Thus, we emphasize the material merging from the national reports and utilize the aggregate charts to organize our discussion patterns, commonalities and significant differences / surprises. The broader analysis incorporates material from all national reports while the quantitative aggregations include information for DK, SL, GR, PL, TR, ES, DK. This was deemed necessary to

numeric data limitations encountered in the FR case study. Below, we analyze the top actors, top debates and their implications for the political fields.

5.5.1. Top actors and organizational patterns

Figure 1 Aggregate and non-normalized data on top vocal actors

Figure 2 Aggregate, normalized data on top vocal actors

The two horizontal bar charts above visualize the top actors captured in the newspaper data across the seven cases. The first chart is based on the aggregate raw data. In the second chart, the data normalized with respect to the size of the data emerging from each context. In the first chart, there is a clear

domination of political parties, NGOs, and advocacy coalitions from Turkey, given the sheer size of the data from Turkey. The organizations entering the top twenty in the non-normalized bar chart are political parties from Greece and Spain. This chart enables us to make some estimations on the centrality of gender debates with respect to countries.

However, because this first chart masks information from national cases where the coded statements are less in number, in the second chart, we have addressed disparities in total concept counts among countries by implementing a normalization procedure to mitigate potential bias from uneven group sizes. This method involved scaling each country's concept counts by a normalization weight, calculated as the ratio of the median total concept count across all countries to the total concept count of the specific country. Using the median—a robust measure less sensitive to extreme values—we minimized the influence of outliers such as Turkey's exceptionally high total count. This approach preserves the internal distribution of concept counts within each country while aligning the overall magnitudes for equitable comparison. The normalization weights and total concept counts for each country are as follows: Turkey (weight = 0.0987, total count = 13,913), Slovenia (weight = 1.9642, total count = 699), Greece (weight = 0.4598, total count = 2,986), Poland (weight = 1.9123, total count = 718), Italy (weight = 2.3795, total count = 577), Spain (weight = 0.6672, total count = 2,058), and Denmark (weight = 1, total count = 1,373). Again, based on the assumption of consistent coding practices and comprehensiveness across countries, this normalization method prevents any single country from disproportionately influencing the results of cross-country comparisons in our analysis.

On the one hand, this chart includes more actors from more country cases. On the other hand, the normalization inevitably loses information in that the weight of coded statements from countries, where the coded statements are less in number, are much higher compared to the weight of coded statements from countries, where the coded statements are higher in number. In other words, in order to overcome dangers of overrepresentation or underrepresentation, the data needs to be evaluated together with the national reports and the qualitative research results from other data streams.

Nevertheless, one broad observation we can make is that in this second chart, political parties emerge as the dominant voices in all national contexts. The significance of the role they play comes across in multiple outputs: they occupy fifteen of the twenty ranks in the above aggregated and normalized data. They also figure substantially in the non-normalized lists of top twenty actors produced separately for each country. Furthermore, when organizations are analyzed with respect to their degree centrality and in-betweenness within the countries, they still continue to occupy the higher positions in these national lists. This is not an unexpected finding because political parties, by definition, aggregate policy debates. The result shows that they speak on multiple gender-related policies and bridge discursive communities which would otherwise have not been connected, therefore, can be considered an indicator of what the DNA captures in terms of political settings. One qualifier to this observation is that the dominance of political parties at the top is partially connected to the choice of corpus. Whereas national media outlets are likely to report on the sayings and doings of political parties, social media data might have shone light on more grassroots and less institutionalized actors. However, we need to qualify this speculation with the expectation that grassroots actors are unlikely to act as policy aggregators, in any case, the way political parties do. An additional interesting observation regards the ideological spectrum at the top: of these fifteen political parties, the researchers have identified seven parties as right wing or center right wing, seven parties as left wing or center left wing, with one identified as center. The distribution of ideological composition varied, however, within individual cases.

Figure 3 Types of organizations at the top, based on 7 country cases top 20 charts

Figure 4 Percentages

The above charts reveal clearly the dominance of political parties. We also see a strong position for NGOs and advocacy groups. By advocacy groups, we mean both more flexibly coalitions of actors and organizations, who band together in advocating for a particular issue, and NGOs. However, movement actors which can be framed as grassroots are not present in the top twenty lists of national cases. In majority of the cases, we see a significant presence of feminist and/or LGBTQI+ rights advocacy, with variations in terms of numbers of and rankings. While in a few cases (Poland, Slovenia), anti-feminist

and anti-gender groups also make it to the top twenty, in the rest of the cases right wing political parties appear to be the placeholders for anti-feminist and anti-gender positions.

There are other organizations, such as business associations (Denmark), professional associations (Spain, Turkey), labor unions (Denmark, Turkey, Italy), universities (Slovenia), and other NGOs with a rights-based focus (Greece) as well as public intellectuals (Denmark) that also have spoken abundantly about gender related policy issues. Added to that is the presence of religious leadership in countries such as Italy, Greece, and Slovenia. The presence of this spectrum in the national lists speaks to two factors: first, who speaks gives indications of the sectors relevant to gender debates (law practitioners speak more when the issues concern legislation, business, and labor actors speak more when the issues concern labor market policies, academics can be heard in matters of freedom of speech and education, etc.). Second, we propose that the fact that gender debates are no longer confined to self-identified feminist versus anti-feminist coalitions reveals the centrality of gender debates to the entire political realm.

The majority of the national reports observed that, in general, the top actors revealed by the DNA output track with other data streams. However, at the same time, there were surprises that the DNA picked up. In some cases, this meant a surprising absence of self-defined anti-feminist and anti-gender organizations at the top of the list, even though their influence in policy debates is detected in qualitative data collection and existing literature (Italy, Turkey). This finding might indicate either the strength of anti-gender/anti-feminist organizations is overestimated in these national contexts, or these organizations pursue more of a kind of backdoor diplomacy to reach their objectives in policy realm, or they have not yet made inroads into mainstream media. In some cases, there were unexpected convergences in specific policy positions as well as general policy statements. For example, surrogacy in Greece was seen in a negative light both by anti-feminist actors as well as gender critical feminists.

5.5.2. Discursive patterns

The codebook for the DNA included two types of concepts. One set of concepts (such as gender equality, women's empowerment and rights, LGBTQI+ rights, and so on) intended to capture the broader ideational positions of actors. A second larger set of concepts intended to delineate thematic areas and such ideational positions into more specific policy debates, regarding existing laws, public and social policies, possible changes to them, as well as their implementation.

Figure 5 Normalized list of top twenty concepts across the cases

The above bar chart is an aggregation of debates from all cases, again normalized with respect to country debate sizes. When the charts for each case are analyzed separately, in all cases, several of the broader concepts make it to the top of the rankings.

One set of debates that can be grouped together are issues pertaining to LGBTQ+ rights: these include the top positioning of LGBTQ+ rights as the concept on which the most number of statements were made in the aggregate data, as well as hate crime legislation, LGBTQ+ visibility in public spaces, gender ideology, gender recognition legislation, promotion of (heterosexual) marriage and family, adoption rights, rights of children of same-sex couples and same sex marriage. Additional relevant debates were also included in the discrete top twenty lists: LGBTQ+ rights in the labor market (Poland), conversion therapy (Poland, Denmark); gender transitioning (Spain); access to surrogacy (Denmark), bathroom access (Denmark), medically assisted reproductive rights (Slovenia).

Violence against women and domestic violence acts, Istanbul Convention, and resources of gender-based violence policy making and implementation also figure prominently and reveal the significance of gender-based violence in the debates in most countries. In addition in single country lists we see other relevant themes such as rape or sexual consent legislation (Denmark, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey), support services for survivors of GBV (Italy, Turkey), penalties for sexual harassment (Denmark), spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse (Spain), child sexual abuse (Turkey), consideration of extenuating circumstances, resources for GBV policy making and implementation, resources for protecting child survivors of sexual abuse (Turkey). The prolificness of this debate reveals the ongoing problems around gender-based violence in all cases.

In many of the cases, the general theme of gender-based violence and connected policy debates were significantly more pronounced (Greece, Italy, Turkey, Spain, Turkey). In one case, labor market related policies were significantly pronounced occupying all the top ranks of the bar-chart (Denmark). Other debates that garnered a lot of attention included repressive state acts, which mainly captured positions on state intervention in and repression of movements, and cultural/community values, which mainly

captured positions that linked or delinked rights and freedoms from stereotypes and/or assumptions about particular religious or minority communities (Turkey, Denmark, Greece, Spain).

While the literature discusses extensively issues around sexual health and reproductive rights, these appeared less pronounced in the top twenty aggregate list with the exception of abortion debates. Abortion debates occupy high ranking positions in Poland, Spain, Italy, and Slovenia. Access to affordable and nondiscriminatory sexual and reproductive health care service is the other relevant theme that showed up in multiple cases (Poland, Spain, Italy) even though it did not make it to the aggregate top twenty list.

Concepts such as women’s rights and empowerment and gender equality, rank high in the aggregate as well as the individual national case reports. Furthermore, there is the appearance of little disagreement in these themes. It appears as if most of the debate participants, regardless of ideological positioning, agreed that women’s rights and gender equality should be promoted, and took a position against violence. A similar result appears in the above aggregate chart with gender equality, women’s rights in the labor market, women’s rights and empowerment placed in high ranks. From an analytical perspective, these findings can indicate a broader degree of consensus on these themes. However, this seeming consensus does not always translate into a similar level of agreement when it comes to specific policy areas whereby such ideas can be realized. The palpable contrast between the two sets inspired some of the reports to reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea without the political intention to put it into practice (Italy, Greece, Slovenia, Turkey).

This observation leads to the question of which themes strike the most controversy. The chart below indicates controversial debates, ranked in terms of the degree of confrontation.

Figure 6 Most controversial debates

In order to produce this aggregate chart, we first brought together the raw data from seven national cases. Then, we calculated the absolute value of the difference between agreements / disagreements for each concept’s adjusted counts. Later, we experimented systematically with different thresholds to

capture the list of concepts that have sufficient data: after trying 25th, 50th, and 75th percentiles in terms of total discussion counts, we chose the median (50th percentile), which corresponds to 33.95 data points for any debate. Hence, any concept with less than 34 adjusted statements is eliminated to capture the frequently used debates. This chart is based on raw data, meaning that data from the Turkish case can be overrepresented, and takes into consideration the number of statements. However, a different list, which does not take into consideration the number of statements, but only looks at the how close the advocates of both sides of the debate are percentage-wise, then top five codes would be sex work, gender transitioning, gender studies programs, freedom of attire and adoption rights.

LGBTQI+ rights is the one generalist area, which figures in the top twenty debates of all national cases while also revealing significantly more controversy than other generalist codes. This presence is translated into this aggregate chart in terms of more specific policy discussions such as adoption rights, LGBTQ+ visibility in public spaces, same sex marriage, LGBTQ+ rights in the labor market, gender recognition rights for minors, gender transitioning, and access to surrogacy. The degree of controversy surrounding multiple policy areas, all falling under the rubric of LGBTQI+ rights, is noteworthy. This can be said to reveal the areas in which anti-gender groups have made inroads into different policies in multiple political contexts. That more actors are audacious in expressing anti-LGBTQI+ rights positions suggest a concerning pattern.

We also see the confrontations in terms of access to abortion, a debate that sparks and/or is reignited in countries, in different periods of time when there are proposals to change existing legislation, for worse or better. This, in fact, is the debate where there are close to equal participants on both sides, revealing the degree to which this right is not safe for women. As mentioned above, we see the prevalence of this debate, particularly in the national reports for the cases France, Poland, Spain, Italy, and Slovenia, suggesting the ongoing fight on this issue.

Another interesting group of debates emerges at the top in terms of gender-based violence. Even though there appears to be consensus on having a violence against women legislation in many countries and overall data, the chart above shows disagreement on specifics of such a legislation (Greece, Poland, Spain, Turkey) such as kinds of punishment and procedures of prosecution, whether spectacular punishment is a solution or not, or whether prosecution can go on based on women's statement and so on.

We also see multiple debates on the nature of the family, how it should be, and under what conditions it can dissolve. These include promotion of motherhood and heterosexual families, same sex marriage, adoption rights, mandatory shared custody, and mediation. These debates encompass discussions on who can form a family, the degree of controversy around which shows the precariousness of rights gained in this area by LGBTQI+ rights. The debates on motherhood and heterosexual families also reveal the extent to which traditional families.

Finally, the debate on cultural/community values needs to be mentioned: this is an interesting debate that captures two different kinds of ideological stances, depending on national context. On the one hand, we have a debate between right-wing anti-feminist and anti-gender actors who promote the ideas of cultural difference and "outside" imposition on national values to reject demands for rights by feminist and LGBTQI+ activists. On the other hand, we have right wing groups who use racist stereotypes, suggesting some communities are not respectful of rights and equality because of their faith or culture, to justify their anti-immigrant stances. Freedom of attire debates also falls into this category of confrontations. Legal pluralism attends to a similar issue, in that the two sides of the debate confront one another on whether there should be a set of national laws that apply to all or whether

religious communities should be allowed to utilize their own laws. The controversy, here, also changes from context to context in terms of the security of the rights women and sexual minorities enjoy regardless of official religious affiliation, degree of sophistication of debates on the role of religion / secularism in defining communities, societies and/or legal rights, and what activists see at stake for both options in terms of minority rights.

Figure 7 Least popular debates

Above is a bar chart on the codes that were least utilized. Most of the concepts here come from country-specific debates, added to the general list of codes at the request of country teams. We see here, again, a specific cluster of codes that address different grievances of LGBTQI+ groups, resources for LGBTQ+ policy making and implementation, ban on artificial hymens, gender-neutral awards, the rights of LGBTQ+ persons in prison, legalization of commercial surrogacy and possibility of more than two legal parents. We also have a series of codes that relate to care work (assessment/visibility of care, paternal leave, menstrual leave). The relative paucity of these debates along with the fact no other codes on care work have made it to the top-ranking positions suggest the relative dearth of discussions of undervaluation and unequal distribution of social reproductive work in public venues such as newspapers. There are also a group of codes that coalesce around the idea of gendered representations (changes in gender stereotypes, gender sensitive portrayal in media and big data, ban on sexist commercials) and their problematization.

5.5.3. Structure of the political fields

The structure of the political fields, in terms of size, the number of participants, the number of debates at hand, and the intensity with which they are debated greatly vary. At one end of the spectrum is Turkey, whose population can go into explaining the intensity of debates, the numbers of participants. But beyond that, other reasons that explain the exceptional situation of Turkey has to do with the recent years which were dominated by public debates on gender-based violence and the campaigns for and against the Istanbul Convention as well as the unique media landscape, which necessitated the sampling of more newspapers. At the other end of the spectrum are countries with a relatively low number of

statements coded (Italy, Poland, and Slovenia). In these countries, we see significantly more articles gathered than debates coded. This partially has to do with debates taking place in areas not covered by the concept list (arts and entertainment), high media coverage emerging more in op-eds, excluded from coding or the conspicuous absence of anti-gender actors from these debates. In total, we sampled 56.840 newspaper articles, and the total number of coded statements was 23.737.

When the different two mode networks of the countries are analyzed, in some countries we see a more fragmented field and there is a diverse range of debates and organizations engaging in them. In these cases, the network maps look fragmented, and the density of connections vary (Denmark, Poland, France, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). The commonality among this group of cases is that the agreements and the disagreements on concepts crisscross and there is not a clear picture of polarization emerging. For others, we see that on certain concepts the agreements and disagreements coalesce in different sections of the map, suggesting more coherent and confronting advocacy communities (Italy, Turkey).

The one mode network maps also have some interesting patterns to glean. In many cases, the anti-gender actors and the extreme right-wing actors lose their significance in these maps. This may suggest a number of things. It could be that while they are vocal on a number of issues, their positions do not have high purchase among the larger civil society terrain. Or they may be speaking on issues that do not attract other participants. Or it could be that some of these actors are more strategically involved in behind-the-door lobbying instead of attempting to gain public legitimacy. In many countries, in one mode maps with thresholds, the political polarization becomes readily visual, depicting a movement-counter-movement dynamic (Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Turkey). Sometimes we can explain this polarization in more general terms of left versus right and in some cases clearer feminist and anti-feminist alliances can be named. In this latter group, it is often the case that the actors voicing feminist positions in debates form larger alliances (Slovenia, Turkey).

In some countries, the algorithm-generated cohesive subgroups overlap with the structuring of the field, as corroborated by other scholarship and/or data streams. These subgroups could be a combination of institutionalized movement actors, non-institutionalized movement actors, other more generalist but progressive organizations in the civil society terrain, political parties and diverse groups which voice anti-feminist and anti-gender positions (Slovenia, Spain, Greece). In cases where the data points are extremely high, the assignment of organizations to different cohesive groups do not reveal consistent institutional characteristics, save for the general positions they take in debates (Turkey).

The maps in national reports also reveal a discursive polarization. Feminist and pro-LGBTQI+ positions coalesce in a separate advocacy community as opposed to anti-feminist and anti-gender positions. In other words, when organizations take on a feminist position in a policy debate, this often means that they are likely to take a feminist position on other debates, as well. In terms of discursive affinities, one pattern that can be gleaned is that while other organizations such as labor unions, rights-based organizations and some other progressive movements are likely to align with feminist positions; religious leaderships, in cases where they are vocal, are more likely to align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions.

5.6. Conclusion

In this section, we summarize the contributions that discourse network analysis makes to the study of feminist and anti-feminist movements. We also summarize the findings and future avenues for research and writing.

The overall strength of DNA for studying feminist and anti-feminist mobilizations is its ability to capture a macro-level perspective. We can glean who speaks, who speaks most and on what issues, to the extent

that they are captured by national newspapers. The outputs generated can provide a quantification of most debated policy areas as well as the degree to which there is agreement or disagreement on specific debates. These enable us to categorize different types of actors and the degree to which the gender debates are relevant / central to the national political terrain. DNA is also able to show the structure of advocacy coalitions, the strength of their discursive connections and the extent to which discursive polarizations exist. In this manner we can determine a broader swath of groups (beyond those publicly known as feminist or anti-feminist or anti-gender) who have ideational affinities. DNA can also reveal discursive ambiguities of political actors, those who adopt feminist positions in some areas and anti-feminist in others.

The most obvious limitation of DNA is that we capture actor positions in a binary fashion, and nuances in public actors' approaches within specific policy debates are lost in the analysis. The latter requires qualitative approaches, as in the interviews and critical frame analysis. Furthermore, DNA utilizes textual data, bounded by newspaper coverage. In other words, less institutionalized and more informal actors, who might occupy more place in social media platforms than mainstream media, are less likely to be visible in this data. This is a limitation in that while actors with more resources and national reach are likely to be reported on, those which remain on the fringes will need other techniques for analysis. The corpus is further limited by the exclusion of opinion pieces with the qualifier that the focus is on policy debates taking place between policy-related organizations. However, in some political contexts, op-ed columnists themselves may be important actors, which play a significant role in steering debates, garnering support for their side, etc. In cases where qualitative techniques reveal this to be the case, DNA can be reorganized to capture the positions of such op-ed writers and/or results of DNA can be combined with critical frame analysis.

In terms of the salient actors the DNA captures, we see a prominent role played by political parties, in terms of the number of times they speak, the number of issues on which they speak and, thus, the top ranks they occupy in both the national reports separately and in the data that aggregates all cases. We also see numerous coalitions of NGOs in the national as well as the aggregate lists. Overall, more positions at the top are occupied by feminist organizations than anti-feminist and anti-gender actors. There are also other organizations such as business associations, professional associations, labor unions, universities, rights-advocacy groups and religious organizations in different countries' top twenty lists. This contextually specific variation parallels the nation-specific debates taking place during the period of analysis. More broadly, it can show the extent to which gender debates are central to the political realm, beyond confrontations between feminist and anti-feminist actors. The patterns and diversities across the cases could lend themselves productively to comparative analyses on who speaks on what issues and what discursive similarities can be identified, also to be supported with CFA component of the research.

General concepts such as women's rights and empowerment, gender equality, women's rights in the labor market appear to generate broad consensus among participants to these debates. However, when the debate is on specific policy areas through which these general objectives can be realized, there is a greater degree of confrontation. Some national reports, thus, reach the conclusion that some actors strategize to hide their policy goals behind more muddled, more general and palatable statements, to pay lip service to the general idea, without the political intention to put it into practice. This finding lends itself nicely to the possibility of collective work on the contrast between generalist positions and policy proposals.

One set of debates that can be grouped together are issues pertaining to LGBTQ+ rights: these include the top positioning of LGBTQ+ rights as the concept on which the greatest number of statements were

made in the aggregate data, as well as other, numerous relevant policy debates in which different aspects of LGBTQ+ rights are promoted or opposed. For this group of debates the degree of confrontation between feminist and anti-feminist / anti-gender positions is strikingly large, not just in specific policy issues, but also for the more general concept of LGBTQ+ rights.

Violence against women and domestic violence acts, Istanbul Convention, and resources of gender-based violence policy making and implementation also figure prominently in most countries. In addition in single country lists we see other relevant themes such as rape or sexual consent, support services for survivors of GBV, penalties for sexual harassment (Denmark), spectacular punishment for GBV and child sexual abuse (Spain), child sexual abuse, consideration of extenuating circumstances, resources for GBV policy making and implementation, resources for protecting child survivors of sexual abuse (Turkey). These findings point to the ongoing problems around gender-based violence in all cases.

Abortion debates occupy high ranking positions in Poland, Spain, Italy, France, and Slovenia. Access to affordable and nondiscriminatory sexual and reproductive health care service is the other relevant theme that showed up in multiple cases (Poland, Spain, Italy) even though it did not make it to the aggregate top twenty list.

The debate on cultural/community values, in conjunction with some articulations of promotion of heterosexual families, freedom of attire, captures place-specific ideological stances. On the one hand, we have a debate between right-wing anti-feminist and anti-gender actors who promote the ideas of cultural difference and “outside” imposition on national values to reject demands for rights by feminist and LGBTQI+ activists (Turkey). On the other hand, we have right wing groups who use racist stereotypes, suggesting some communities are not respectful of rights and equality because of their faith or culture, to justify their anti-immigrant stances.

When the different two mode networks of the countries, reported in the national reports, are analyzed, in some countries we see a more fragmented field and there is a diverse range of debates and organizations engaging in them (Denmark, Poland, Greece, Slovenia, Spain). In this group of cases the agreements and the disagreements on concepts crisscross and there is not a clear picture of polarization emerging. For others, we see more coherent and confronting advocacy communities revealing a greater degree of polarization (Italy, Turkey).

Nevertheless, the one-mode network maps reveal that when organizations take on a feminist position in a policy debate, they are likely to take a feminist position on other debates, as well. While other organizations such as labor unions, rights-based organizations and some other progressive actors are likely to align with feminist positions; religious leaderships, in cases where they are vocal, are more likely to align with anti-feminist and anti-gender positions

In the one mode network maps in the national reports, the anti-gender actors and the extreme right-wing actors lose their significance. This may suggest several things. It could be that while they are vocal on a few issues, their positions do not have high purchase among the larger civil society terrain. Or they may be speaking on issues that do not attract other participants. Or it could be that some of these actors are more strategically involved in behind-the-door lobbying instead of attempting to gain public legitimacy. In many countries, in one mode maps with thresholds, the political polarization becomes readily visual, depicting a movement-counter movement dynamic (Italy, Slovenia, Poland, Turkey). Sometimes we can explain this polarization in more general terms of left versus right and in some cases clearer feminist and anti-feminist alliances can be named. In this latter group, it is often the case that the actors voicing feminist positions in debates form larger alliances (Slovenia, Turkey).

References

- Barranco, J., & Wisler, D. (1999). Validity and systematicity of newspaper data in event analysis. *European Sociological Review*, 15(3), 301-322.
- Leifeld, P. (2013). Reconceptualizing major policy change in the advocacy coalition framework: A discourse network analysis of German pension politics. *Policy Studies Journal*, 41(1), 169-198.

Appendices

- [SNA Guidelines – Workshop 1](#)
- [SNA Guidelines – Workshop 2](#)
- [DNA Guidelines – Newspaper selection](#)
- [DNA – Concept list](#)

6. Individual Country Reports

This section collects the country reports, with a link for each research stream (interviews, CFA, DNA).

6.1. Denmark

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.2. France

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.3. Greece

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.4. Italy

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.5. Poland

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.6. Slovenia

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.7. Spain

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)

6.8. Turkey

- [Interview country report](#)
- [CFA country report](#)
- [DNA country report](#)